

D6.3 - Final Report on Use Cases and community involvement

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Deliverable Abstract
<p>This deliverable reports on both technical and social major achievements from the Use cases involved in the WP6 EOOSC-Pillar project as well as on the initiatives set up to enhance the involvement and participation from users' communities.</p>

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Terminology *not exhaustive*

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology / Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
CINES	Centre Informatique National de l'Enseignement Supérieur
CMCC	Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
CMIP6	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (Phase 6)
CND3D	Conservatoire National des Données 3D
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CNR-IOM	CNR - Istituto Officina dei Materiali
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
DKRZ	Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum
ECAS	ENES Climate Analytics Service
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-Pillar	Coordination and Harmonisation of National and Thematic Initiatives to Support EOSC project
ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation
eTDR	European Trusted Digital Repository
F2DS	Federated FAIR Data Space
FAIR data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable data
HAL	Hyper Articles en Ligne (Open Science repository)
HPC	High Performance Computing
INFN	Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
INRIA	Institut national de recherche en informatique et automatique
INSERM	Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale
IS-ENES	Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling
LOD	Link Open Data
NEP	NFFA Europe Project
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PID	Persistent Identifier
POC	Proof of Concept
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
UC	Use Case
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VAP	Virtual Analysis Platform
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

WP	Work Package
WG	Working Group
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

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Executive summary

This deliverable, D6.3 “Final Report on Use Cases and community involvement” reports on both technical and social major achievements from the Use cases involved in the WP6 EOSC-Pillar project. The present document has been structured around the following points: 1) the description of the activities carried out throughout the project since their inception, pointing out the results achieved in relation to the plan of actions; 2) the list and the description of major initiatives in terms of communication, outreach, training and capacity building against the targeted communities and beyond; and finally, 3) the synthesis of common and cross-cutting activities and developments implemented in collaboration with other Use cases (UC) or Work packages (WP).

As stated in the previous WP6 deliverable, D6.2 (https://zenodo.org/record/6541565#.Y3igQy_pNpQ), due to the six-months extension of the WP6, the deadline to submit the demonstrators shifted from M24 to M30. The present document also presents possible updates of the demonstrators delivered by the WP6 Use cases, which were not included in the previous deliverable.

1 Introduction

WP6 managed 9 Use cases (UC) based on the requirements of scientific communities intended to improve the usage of data in a FAIR perspective having in view the possibility to make their developments general, scalable and accessible to other communities through EOSC. For that purpose, activities, firstly, have been focused on the implementation of functional demonstrators of the services set up in the UCs that, finally, have been tested against the targeted communities.

In addition, the initial set of scientific Use cases has been expanded through an open call for participation, inviting communities and their developers to bring forward potential services to enhance the portfolio of the project. An overview of the five “new” use cases and the relevant support by EOSC-Pillar is provided in a dedicated paragraph of the present deliverable.

Bearing in mind that the final objective was to make the UCs demonstrators scalable and their developments useful to their targeted communities and potentially useful to other communities having similar needs and requirements, a particular attention has been paid to cross-cutting interactions within WP6 and other parts of the project as well. Since the WP6 deliverable D6.1 “State of the art and communities needs report from Use cases” (<https://zenodo.org/record/3894677>), two main analysis criteria have been deemed particularly relevant: (i) collaboration and common developments with other UCs, and (ii) possible links with other technical Work packages, namely WP5 (Data layer) and WP7 (Infrastructure layer). During the implementation of the project activities, links with other Work packages, such as WP4 on “national initiatives and trans-national services”, have been identified.

Finally, a session of the present document gathers all the references, scientific publications and articles related to EOSC-Pillar WP6 Use cases activities and developments, that have been produced and published during the entire life-cycle of the project.

2 The Use cases

This session consists of (i) the most recent description of actions in the framework of each WP6 Use cases, and (ii) the description of initiatives taken up after M24 (or M30 in some cases) with a particular attention to those initiatives oriented to enhance the participation and the involvement of users' communities.

2.1 UC6.1: “Defining Procedures/Services to enforce Data provenance for thematic communities and beyond”

2.1.1 The UC description

General description and main objectives

Due to the increasing complexity of data analysis workflows, provenance management is a key component to support the re-use of scientific data. Alongside findability, accessibility and interoperability, the reusability of data constitutes a pillar of the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) and in this regard rich and reliable provenance is essential to ensure that. The Use case 6.1 (**Defining procedures and services to enforce data provenance for thematic communities and beyond**) aims at elaborating cross-domain, FAIR-oriented procedures and recommendations to enforce data provenance by considering the needs coming from two scientific domains: Materials Science/Nanoscience and Climate Science. In such a context, the **W3C PROV**¹ standard has been considered as a recommended family of specifications for tracking processes and responsibilities as well as describing provenance structures within complex experiments and large workflows on scientific data. Starting from the W3C PROV data model and ontology, the PROV Core concepts have been adapted and extended to match with the existing scientific data services considered, in order to enhance provenance capabilities, thus addressing FAIR-oriented full provenance management. The demonstrator, along with the motivation, the main objectives and the activities carried out throughout the project, is fully described in the deliverable D6.2. However, following the project extension to M42, it was further enhanced, thus strengthening the linkages with other UCs and WPs. Below is a brief description of the demonstrator, including the activities carried out in the last part of the project and the results achieved. For any detail concerning specific topics, please refer to the D6.2 deliverable.

Figure 1: PROV Core Structures

As mentioned above, the demonstrator exploits the W3C PROV standard as a recommended family of specification for tracking well-structured provenance information within the scientific data services. The PROV Family of Documents defines a data model (**PROV-DM**)² along with the corresponding serializations (i.e., **PROV-N**³ as a notation aimed at human consumption, **PROV-O**⁴ as the ontology for mapping the PROV data model to RDF, **PROV-XML**⁵ and **PROV-JSON**⁶ as XML schema and JSON representation for the PROV data model, respectively) and other supporting definitions to enable the

¹ W3C PROV: <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

² PROV-DM: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-dm-20130430/>

³ PROV-N: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-n-20130430/>

⁴ PROV-O: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-o-20130430/>

⁵ PROV-XML: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/NOTE-prov-xml-20130430/>

⁶ PROV-JSON: <https://www.w3.org/Submission/prov-json/>

inter-operable interchange of provenance information in heterogeneous environments such as the Web. Further details about the PROV data model and its core structures are provided in D6.2.

Materials science/Nanoscience demonstrator

The main objective of this demonstrator is to provide guidelines and recommendations on how to manage the aspect of data provenance for the wide community behind the NFFA-Europe PILOT Project (NEP)⁷.

The initial activities consisted with the creation of a database to store scientific images metadata and the development of a web service to visually explore these metadata through interactive tools. The objective here was the FAIRification of a scientific archive of Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM) images, and the creation of a curated dataset to allow researchers to build the provenance of data.

Description of services provided:

- **STM Metadata Database:** a data service to store scientific images metadata. It helps the discovery of images on the whole dataset by selecting different metadata values as filters, thus improving the findability and accessibility.
- **STM Metadata Explorer:** an easy-to-use and interactive web service that researchers can use to interact with the STM Metadata Database and explore images metadata through interactive and downloadable plots. The crucial component of this web service is metadata enrichment with information on sample composition, obtained with machine learning techniques. It allows visualization and download functionalities directly in the web browser. This service is integrated within **Trieste Advanced Data Services (TriDAS)**⁸, designed to enable advanced data services connected to scientific data resources to help researchers in their work.

On top of these data services, during the FAIRification workflow, was applied W3C PROV standard to describe the provenance of metadata, from the original STM images to the ones curated and available on the TriDAS website. The source code⁹, as well as a list of all used software package are publicly available and annotated in the provenance metadata.

The different components concerning the workflow of the principal events performed during the FAIRification process of STM images, from the Raw data generated by Omicron Variable Temperature STM (VT-STM) measurements to the final image, were mapped with the W3C PROV core concepts.

For the mapping, as components of PROV-DM were considered: entities and activities, derivations, and agents with their responsibilities.

Figure 2: Graphical representation of the provenance workflow of STM images based on PROV-DM structures.

⁷ NFFA-Europe PILOT project: <https://www.nffa.eu/news/project-updates/pilot-nep/>

⁸ Tridas: <https://tridas.nffa.eu/>

⁹ GitHub STM images: https://github.com/t0m-R/STM_images

The process of the FAIRification activities and the subsequent mapping with W3C PROV components leads to the provenance workflow presented in Figure 2. Then, a practical implementation of the workflow was conducted by using a PROV Python Library for W3C Provenance Data Model¹⁰. The provenance document created in Python was then exported in a JSON representation for PROV, PROV-JSON, thus providing a compact and accurate representation of PROV that is particularly suitable for interchanging PROV documents, allowing reproducibility and interoperability.

The dataset containing 7287 STM images, together with their provenance description was published on Zenodo¹¹. The source code¹² used is available on GitHub. Furthermore, all the work performed so far is described in the paper ‘Towards the FAIRification of Scanning Tunneling Microscopy Images’ (Rodani et al., 2022).

Part of the terms used in the provenance workflow has been already agreed upon among the NFFA Europe community as they have been defined in the NFFA-Europe Glossary¹³ developed in collaboration with the Joint Lab “Integrated Model and Data Driven Materials Characterization” (MDMC) of the Helmholtz Association of German Research Centers. In addition, from January 2022, we started to participate on the co-development of the MDMC-NEP Prov ontology¹⁴, where the STM demonstrator served as the first application use case. The ontology contains high-level provenance information to describe or annotate the entire experimental workflow.

The implementation details of the work done so far, in particular the PROV implementation, are somewhat specific to the present STM case study, but, in principle, they can be easily generalized and applied to a large number of scanning microscopy experiments (SEM, AFM, etc.). Thus, the services listed until now were presented to other project partners in the Materials Science field, who are also working in digitalisation processes but applied to other domains (e.g. mechanical testing, modelling and simulation). While their focus had been on the provenance of the physical processes until now i.e. the different tests and changes that a sample goes through; the interest in also documenting the semantic enrichment process was shared, especially in the context of FAIR data (and in particular Reproducibility). For instance, projects such as StahlDigital (from the German platform MaterialDigital) or UrWerk (a Fraunhofer collaboration project among three institutes) are clear candidates that could benefit from recording and standardising such provenance information. Unfortunately, given the current projects and timelines, no further application was feasible in the frame of the EOSC-Pillar project. Nevertheless, future developments and integrations are being studied.

Climate Science demonstrator

Climate research makes use of lots of data coming from the modelling and observational climate communities. In this domain, provenance management plays a key role both for numerical end-to-end simulations at data center level and in the inner data analytics workflows. In such a context, provenance tracking has been addressed at two different levels complying with the W3C PROV standard:

¹⁰ Huynh Trung Dong. Prov Python. (2014). Available at: <https://github.com/trungdong/prov>

¹¹ Tommaso Rodani, Elda Osmenaj, Alberto Cazzaniga, Mirco Panighel, Cristina Africh, & Stefano Cozzini. (2021). Dataset of Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM) images of graphene on nickel (1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5808724>

¹² Github source code: https://github.com/t0m-R/STM_images

¹³ NFFA Glossary. Available at: <https://www.nffa.eu/apply/data-policy/glossary>

¹⁴ Materials-Data-Science-and-Informatics/MDMC-NEP-top-level-ontology: This repository collects the ongoing work towards the development of the ontology on common terms defined for the MDMC Joint Lab and NEP. (github.com)

- the first one (first-level) refers to the whole end-to-end scientific workflow including a proper reference to input and output datasets via PIDs;
- the second one (second-level) provides a focus on some first-level tasks, like those regarding data analytics, which can be represented themselves as workflows of micro-tasks and may usually consist of hundreds or thousands of analytics operators.

The demonstrator was initially built on top of the IT services and resources proposed by national infrastructures involved in the project. Specifically, it was built on top of the **ENES Climate Analytics Service** (ECAS)¹⁵, one of the EOSC-Hub¹⁶ Thematic Services as well as a Compute Service in the IS-ENES3¹⁷ project. ECAS enables scientific end-users to perform data analysis experiments on large volumes of multidimensional data by exploiting a PID-enabled, server-side, and parallel approach. Moreover, it provides access to a set of specific CMIP¹⁸ variable-centric collections. These datasets, mainly related to CMIP5 and CMIP6 data products, are downloaded and kept in sync with the ESGF¹⁹ data archive.

The ECAS instance hosted at CMCC provides support for fast computations through the Ophidia²⁰ analytics engine, which enables data-intensive analysis exploiting advanced parallel computing techniques and smart data distribution methods.

The example below (Figure 3) shows a climate analytics workflow consisting of the following tasks:

- *Subset data*: data subsetting over the time dimension (from 2090 to 2100) through the CDO (Climate Data Operators)²¹ tool set;
- *Compute max*: temporal aggregation (e.g. maximum over the whole time series for each point in the spatial domain) through Xarray²²;
- *Generate PID*: generation of a persistent identifier to be attached to the output file;
- *Compute Tropical Nights index*: computation of a climate index (e.g. Tropical Nights, the number of days where the daily minimum temperature is above a reference temperature, e.g. 20°C) through the Ophidia framework²³ and its Python bindings PyOphidia²⁴;
- *Visualize the result*: result visualization through Matplotlib²⁵ and Cartopy²⁶.

¹⁵ ENES Climate Analytics Service: <https://is.enes.org/sdm-climate-analytics-data/#cas-cmcc>

¹⁶ EOSC-Hub: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/>

¹⁷ IS-ENES3: <https://is.enes.org/>

¹⁸ CMIP (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project), <https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip>. A collaborative framework designed to improve knowledge of climate change.

¹⁹ ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation), a federated data infrastructure for the management, dissemination and analysis of model output and observational data.

²⁰ S. Fiore, D. Elia, C. Palazzo, F. Antonio, A. D’Anca, I. Foster, G. Aloisio, “Towards High Performance Data Analytics for Climate Change”, ISC High Performance 2019, LNCS Springer, 2019

²¹ CDO: <https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo/>

²² Xarray: <https://docs.xarray.dev/en/stable/>

²³ Ophidia, <https://ophidia.cmcc.it>. A CMCC Foundation research project addressing big data challenges for eScience.

²⁴ PyOphidia: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/PyOphidia>

²⁵ Matplotlib: <https://matplotlib.org>

²⁶ Cartopy: <https://scitools.org.uk/cartopy/docs/latest/>

Figure 3: Example of climate analytics workflow

The main idea is to navigate the first level provenance to have a complete understanding of the overall high-level end-to-end workflow and then have the opportunity to drill-down into some specific analytics tasks (e.g. climate index computation) to get more detailed information about their internal workflow in terms of micro-tasks or analytics operators. In such a context we can refer to two-level workflows, as two-level provenance management accordingly.

First-level provenance management

The objective of the demonstrator is to provide guidance and tools to scientists for the generation of W3C PROV compatible provenance descriptions as part of their scientific climate data analysis notebooks. The main focus of this demonstrator is to provide a concrete starting point to integrate the EOSC-Pillar use cases in 6.1, 6.2 and 6.8, by integrating the aspects of provenance generation with PIDs and PID collections (as part of provenance records) and science Jupyter notebooks e.g. hosted on the D4Science VRE²⁷. Climate scientists need simple templates and rules they can follow to ease the provisioning of PROV records in addition to generated analysis results which they want to share, or which should be used in downstream community use cases (e.g. by the climate impact research community). The approach is prototyped for initial demonstrator scientific use cases developed as part of the Task 6.2 use cases (Agile FAIR data for environmental sciences) which are accessible as part of the ECAS service²⁸ and are also accessible via the D4Science virtual research environment. The image below shows the first-level provenance associated with the high-level end-to-end workflow represented in Fig. 3.

²⁷ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/web/eoscpillar4earthscience>

²⁸ <https://is.enes.org/sdm-climate-analytics-data/>

Figure 4: First-level provenance information based on W3C PROV specifications

Second-level provenance management

To account for in-depth provenance support within the climate processing services, a second-level provenance management complying with the W3C PROV standard has been elaborated, thus addressing FAIR principles at a finer granularity.

In the last part of the project, the containerized version of the Ophidia framework²⁹ (including the back-end components only) has been properly extended³⁰ to enable the provenance support and bring it into the [EOSCPillar4EarthScience³¹](https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillar4earthscience) VRE (Virtual Research Environment), an open, cloud-enabled computing environment deployed on the EOSC-Pillar Gateway (see "Demonstrator #6.2 - Agile FAIR Data for Environment and Earth System Communities"), thus allowing scientific end-users from Earth environment & Geosciences communities to run data analysis workflows with a stronger provenance support (so called second-level) able to track analytics activity at the level of single operator. In addition, some of the datasets used to set up the proof-of-concept climate use cases were aggregated through the EOSC-Pillar Federated FAIR Data Space ([F2DS³²](https://f2ds.eosc-pillar.eu/login)) and published into the D4Science [EOSC-Pillar Data Catalog³³](https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillarresdatactlg/catalogue).

²⁹ <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/ophidia-container>

³⁰ <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/ophidia-container/tree/main/single-node-backend-hub>

³¹ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillar4earthscience>

³² <https://f2ds.eosc-pillar.eu/login>

³³ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillarresdatactlg/catalogue>

Figure 5: Climate datasets published into the EOSC-Pillar Data Catalog

A Python application was developed allowing users to retrieve the provenance documents related to a specific analytics workflow in several formats, such as XML, JSON, RDF or graphical format, based on the information about the executed tasks that is tracked by the Ophidia server. This application exploits the PROV³⁴ Python library - an implementation of the W3C PROV Data Model supporting PROV-O (RDF), PROV-XML, PROV-JSON import/export - to map the ECAS/Ophidia concepts into the proper W3C PROV concepts.

Considering the workflow in Fig. 3, the computation of the Tropical Nights climate index is itself a workflow of several micro-tasks (analytics operators) that can be further inspected and explored. In this regard, users can run the developed Python application using the Ophidia logs made available on the client side to get a provenance tracking at a finer granularity.

Figure 6: Python application integrated into the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE to get second-level provenance information based on W3C PROV specifications

³⁴ PROV library: <https://pypi.org/project/prov/>

Figure 7: PROV-O graphical illustration of the fine-grained provenance information captured at the second level of the Tropical Nights workflow based on W3C PROV specifications

Figure 8: PROV-JSON and PROV-XML documents related to the second-level provenance information captured for the Tropical Nights workflow

Further information including the code of the PROV Python application developed within the task as well as an example on how to use it can be found on the corresponding [github repository](#)³⁵.

2.1.2 Communities involvement

During the project, different online materials describing the use case services and results were provided:

- **UC1 page on the EOSC-Pillar website**³⁶, thus contributing to the campaign on "Use cases Showcasing Diverse Use Cases & Community-Driven Pilots".
- **EOSC-Pillar use case factsheet**³⁷, published in the EOSC-Pillar Zenodo community.
- **Guidelines for researchers**³⁸, published into the EOSC-Pillar Training and Support Catalogue and the EOSC-Pillar Zenodo community.

Outreach and potential use by other communities

In addition, several papers, posters and talks were given in the context of scientific conferences and workshops:

- **Digital poster**³⁹ at the TNC22 Conference (13-17 June 2022, Trieste, Italy).
- **Scientific Paper**: Tommaso Rodani, Elda Osmenaj, Alberto Cazzaniga, Mirco Panighel, Cristina Africh, Stefano Cozzini; Towards the FAIRification of Scanning Tunneling Microscopy Images. Data Intelligence 2022; doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00164.
- **Talk**: presentation of the STM demonstrator during the PNR project workshop with participants from the NFFA-Europe PILOT community (materials science/nanoscience).
- **Digital Poster**⁴⁰: Ahmad Zainul Ihsan, Said Fathalla, Rossella Aversa, Mehrdad Jalali, Mirco Panighel, Elda Osmenaj, Volker Hofmann, Stefan Sandfeld; Domain level ontology design: DISO and MDMC-NEP Prov at the Helmholtz metadata conference, 6 October 2022.

³⁵ <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/ophidia-provenance>

³⁶ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/use-cases/defining-procedures-services-enforce-data-provenance-thematic-communities>

³⁷ EOSC-Pillar use case factsheet: <https://zenodo.org/record/6725047#.YzV1HS8QPyg>

³⁸ Guidelines for researchers: https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCPillarTrainingAndSupport/uc1_guidelines_for_researchers_defining_procedures_and_services_to_enforce_data_provenance_for_them (<https://zenodo.org/record/6827750#.YzVqoC8QPyg>)

³⁹ Poster TNC22: <https://tnc22.geant.org/posters/#c228>

⁴⁰ Poster at HMC 2022: https://events.hifis.net/event/469/contributions/3214/attachments/798/1372/2022-10-05_HMCConference_poster_domain_and_application_level_ontology_design_final.pdf

2.2 UC6.2: “Agile FAIR data for Earth Environment and Geosciences communities”

2.2.1 The UC description

EOSC-Pillar WP6 UC2 “Agile Fair Data for Earth Environment and Geosciences communities” is based on the following statement: Earth environment and geosciences require a large panel of observations from models, experiments, in-situ and satellite data. Data resulting from these observations is managed and stored in distributed, domain-dependent or discipline-dependent repositories that rely on several national or European infrastructures. Considering the permanent growth in data volume and number, it is quite difficult and time-consuming to search, access, download and process environmental data from several disciplines and domains to perform integrated analysis, yet of primary importance for several studies with large societal impacts: climate change, agriculture and food, human safety near the coast...

In this context, the use-case’s goal was to set up a Virtual Data Analysis Platform, facilitating data discovery, access and processing for users from environment and Earth system communities, allowing them to perform on-demand cross-domain or inter-domain comprehensive studies, regardless of their own storage and computing facilities or domain of expertise.

In order to meet this challenge, the use-case has focused on four main activities:

1. developing Data Sciences Notebooks that offers a web-based processing environment for scientists and data analysts using [PANGEO](https://pangeo.io/)’s environment⁴¹
2. implementing Data services, to speed up and facilitate data access from several domains
3. developing a cross-domain catalog to enhance discovery of heterogeneous data from several Earth domains
4. implementing these services on efficient IT infrastructures suited for on-demand Big Data processing

As a result, a Virtual Data Analysis Platform (VDAP) demonstrating the aforementioned services was deployed on D4Science infrastructure service: EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE⁴². The VDAP proposes a solution to facilitate researcher’s on-demand discovery, access, analysis and processing of heterogeneous Big-data from different data sources, domains and types, through the following workflow:

- *User discovers data and associated services via a cross-domain data catalog (EOSC-Pillar FFDS data catalogue)*
- *User accesses EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE on D4Science IT infrastructure*
- *User benefits from pre-defined analysis scripts or develops new scripts using specific software packages adapted to Big Data analysis (PANGEO) in a Virtual Research Environment*
- *User easily accesses analysis-ready data from different national repositories, without downloading and converting the data*
- *User runs their analysis on-demand on remote (D4Science) computing facilities*
- *User can visualize the results online and download them*
- *User can share his work with colleagues or other data analysts/researchers*

The content of the VDAP, its technical implementation and the access procedures are described in the “EOSCPILLAR4EarthScience VRE QuickStart” guide⁴³.

⁴¹ <https://pangeo.io/>

⁴² <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/group/eoscpillar4earthscience>

⁴³ Antonio, Fabrizio, Vernet, Marine, Kulüke, Marco, Sudre, Joël, Harscoat, Valérie, Quéric, Antoine, Maudire, Gilbert, &

The progress made by the UC's partners throughout the project regarding each of these activities is summarized in the following points.

1) **Easier and faster Earth environment Big-data processing and analysis**

In order to simplify programming of Big-data for different Earth system domains, the UC's partners decided to use PANGEO's open-source software stack. The packages made available by this community to access data and perform analysis can be deployed on HPC or Cloud clusters, within Python Notebooks.

A total of 8 Data Sciences Jupyter Notebooks were developed by the UC's partners, describing and demonstrating how to use PANGEO's software stack to easily search and access data, perform multisource data analysis, and visualize it online. These notebooks are described in D6.2⁴⁴ and in the EOSCPillar4EarthSciences VRE Quick Start guide. For example, the "temperature_threshold_analysis" Notebook developed by DKRZ shows how to search and exploit historical or Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSP) experiments from Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) climate models to count annual summer days for the user's year and area of interest.

Through the VDAP, users can access, execute and reuse on-demand the 8 ready-to-use Data Sciences Jupyter Notebooks developed by the UC, or use the PANGEO's software stack made available in the virtual research environment to develop their own Notebooks and run them on their datasets of interest.

The Notebooks make use of several PANGEO's packages, such as Intake, which allows for a transparent and easy access to distributed datasets regardless of their location, Xarray, to work with labelled multidimensional arrays of data or Dask, to provide parallel computing.

Since D6.2 publication, CMCC has worked to offer an instance of the [Ophidia](#)⁴⁵ [High-Performance Data Analytics framework](#) as a second service to users in the VDAP. Users can now easily integrate an Ophidia-based analysis into a more articulated data analytics workflow (by leveraging the [PyOphidia](#)⁴⁶ Python package, included in the Python-based software stack, as a programmatic interface to the Ophidia server-side components) and get fine-grained provenance information compliant with the W3C PROV standard.

All packages available in the VDAP are listed and described in the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE QuickStart, as well as the PyOphidia Notebook for Ophidia-based climate data analysis use-cases.

The VDAP is powered by D4Science IT facilities. Each user of the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE has access to a web-based processing environment and can chose between different server's options, depending on the resources he want to access: small, medium or large amount of CPU and RAM. Three additional server profiles are available in the VDAP to fit the new functionalities offered through the CMCC PyOphidia Data Science Notebook.

2) **Easier and faster access to Earth environment Big-data**

Ensuring fast and easy on-demand access to voluminous and distributed datasets from Earth Environment and geosciences was an important challenge of the UC. Indeed, due to the size and number of data now available for Earth Observation and modelling, agile access solutions avoiding multiple data download and copy are required to save time and storage resources. It is also of great use when dealing with continuously updated time series, such as ARGO datasets. In addition,

Kindermann, Stephan. (2022). EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE - Quick Start. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7128695>

⁴⁴ Rizzo, Alessandro, Pierkot, Christelle, Vernet, Marine, Sudre, Joël, von Hartrott, Philipp, & Berberi, Lisana. (2022). EOSC-Pillar D6.2 - Demonstrators and success stories from the use cases. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6541565>

⁴⁵ <https://ophidia.cmcc.it>

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/PyOphidia>

processing data from different Earth domains requires time to understand the formats and resources to convert them into suitable common data format.

To deal with this issue, two different data services were tested by the UC, [OpenStack Object Storage](#) (Swift⁴⁷) for climate data and [iRODS](#)⁴⁸ for marine data. Different data access methods were explored, such as scheduled or on-demand synchronization or data subsetting. The one chosen (on-demand data synchronization) allows users to read the data directly through iRODS or Swift when requested, thus improving data transfer speed. Two additional Python packages were implemented by DKRZ and Ifremer to convert dataset into cloud-optimized [Zarr](#)⁴⁹ and [Parquet](#)⁵⁰ format, better suited for Big Data processing.

The two data services have been connected to the VDAP, but due to security issues with the iRODS instance, only [DKRZ Swift](#)⁵¹ is implemented for the users, the marine data and a limited set of climate data exploited by the UC had to be uploaded directly to the VDAP.

3) **Easier data discovery**

The UC's partners have chosen to use the Federated FAIR Data Space (FFDS) service as a common cross-domain catalogue for all Earth system and environmental data of the UC. This service, developed by EOSC-Pillar WP5 and tested by the UC, harvest EOSC-Pillar partners metadata and allow them to map it into a common metadata model, DCAT and its geospatial extension, GEO-DCAT-AP. Through FFDS, the data is FAIRified and published in a FAIR Data Point. The FFDS data catalog harvests automatically the FAIR Data Point and allows data discovery through various search filters. The EOSCPillar4EarthScience VDAP also has a data catalogue regrouping all Earth observation and environmental data used in the VDAP. It is synchronized automatically with the FFDS data catalog.

UC's partners have worked to ensure the connection of their catalogues and a correct mapping of their dataset descriptions into GEO-DCAT AP model through FFDS metadata repository API.

All UC2 datasets described through the API have been published into FFDS data catalogue and the associated EOSCPILLAR4EarthScience VDAP data catalogue. The user is therefore able to discover, through a single entry-point, all Earth environment and geosciences data available in the VDAP on his temporal and spatial area of interest.

From one Earth domain to another, data is described using different metadata models or ontologies, through several catalogues using different protocols. In addition, the catalogs describing this data are set up at different level: for example, Odatis marine data catalogue proposes to discover and access collections of datasets. The ESGF catalogue offers climate data simulations descriptions that are at a collection of datasets level, but do not contain all descriptive elements about the data. The collections of datasets are described in DKRZ «Search & access» catalog (used at data analysis level), with rich content-related metadata such as variable or experiment. In order to have both types of information available and ensure an easy discovery of climate data in the cross-domain catalog, DKRZ developed a [STAC API](#) to connect the two catalogs levels, but the connection with FFDS metadata repository could not be realised due to time constraints.

4) **Implementation of a VDAP on IT infrastructures suited for on-demand Big Data processing**

In order to offer a complete workflow from data discovery to analysis results, the UC's partners, after a first test on their own IT infrastructures, have deployed the VDAP (EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE) on

⁴⁷ <https://wiki.openstack.org/wiki/Swift>

⁴⁸ <https://irods.org/>

⁴⁹ <https://zarr.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

⁵⁰ <https://parquet.apache.org/>

⁵¹ <https://docs.dkrz.de/doc/datastorage/swift/index.html>

external facilities, making use of D4Science VRE service and associated storage and computing power. Among the different infrastructures and cloud services offered by EOSC-Pillar WP7 partners, the UC has chosen to deploy the platform on D4Science service for the following reasons:

- first, D4Science provides, along with storage and computing resources, a cloud-based virtual research environment service with JupyterHub option that one can parameter and manage easily, allowing not to start from scratch. It also offers a shared workspace, allowing for sharing and reuse of Notebooks and results among VDAP users.
- Second, D4Science VRE service has an associated AAI service that is quite useful to deal with different issues, such as security and user management.
- Third, D4Science VRE service also provides a data catalogue, allowing for fast discovery of cross-domain Earth data, and this data catalogue is automatically enriched with EOSC-Pillar FFDS FAIR Data Point content. Since the partners chose to test the FFDS service as cross-domain catalogue for the use-case, it was an easy way to test a complete workflow.

However, while sufficient for demonstration use, the resources offered by the D4Science service would be too limited to perform Big-data analysis at a larger scale. There is a need for a solution offering additional distributed computing and storage power in an e-infrastructure better suited for parallel computing.

The UC has started to explore a second implementation on CINES IT facilities, but the partners have faced difficulties regarding security protocols inherent to national computing centres, and could not investigate further by lack of time and human resources.

What could be improved or explored in the future?

How to go further:

- Explore additional solutions to bring together data and processing:
 - o Enhance remote data access through iRODS or other data access services allowing to read directly the data close to processing without moving it.
 - o Containerisation on multiple clusters, for example, related on Kubernetes.
- Additional IT infrastructure, more suited to parallel processing of Big-geosciences-data.
- Testing scheduling services that make it transparent to the user which infrastructure provider the service is deployed with (while selecting the best provider on criteria of service availability or required computing & storage resources).

2.2.2 Communities involvement

The UC's partners have engaged in several communication and outreach activities in order to present the use-case's activities to the Earth environment, geosciences, and data communities.

Indeed, the Use Case was presented over the last 3 years at different national or European events, such as the 2021 EGI conference⁵², and the German Data Days in 2022, as well as internally at EOSC-France event or in the Data Terra infrastructure for example.

The concept of the use-case and its relation toward the FAIR principles were also addressed through outreach activities: production of a flyer⁵³ and a podcast session about FAIR Data for Earth Sciences⁵⁴ as support material for the Ambassador program coordinated by EOSC-Pillar WP2. The aim of these communication materials is twofold: present the challenges addressed by the use-case and give a concrete example of EOSC research story, considering Open Science and FAIR principles.

⁵² <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU21/EGU21-2442.html>

⁵³ Kulüke, Marco, Czuray, Marie, Geistberger, Julia Sophie, Calamai, Lorenzo, & Giuffrida, Maria. (2022). EOSC-Pillar Ambassadors Programme - Use case: FAIR Data for Earth Sciences. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6584737>

⁵⁴ <https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/FAIR-Data-for-Earth-Sciences-e1norjm>

A webpage⁵⁵ on EOSC-Pillar website is also available, alongside with the Use-case factsheet⁵⁶, poster⁵⁷ and demonstrations videos published on EOSC-Pillar YouTube channel.

In order to engage with external potential users, a specific 2-hour workshop session was held in May 2022 with 9 selected scientists (developers, data analysts) from the climate and marine research communities. The workshop was organized with the help of EOSC-Pillar T5.3 and T5.4. The presentations focused on FAIR principles and how the use-case VDAP demonstrator, EOSCPillar4EarthSciences VRE, try to address FAIR-compliance. The participants were given access to the VDAP and a specific user-guide documenting how to use the VDAP beforehand. A live test session of the VDAP was organized. Feedback were collected from discussions engaged during the workshop, and through an online questionnaire sent out to all participants at the end of the workshop. The user guide is available in the EOSC-Pillar Training and Support catalogue⁵⁸ and on the Zenodo repository⁵⁹. All participants agreed on the problems faced and the usefulness of the solution proposed by UC2 to facilitate the work of scientists from the Earth Environment and Geosciences community, in the EOSC context. They were rather pleased with the VDAP functionalities (notebooks, large docker container, possibility to deploy a Dask cluster), the available Data Sciences stack and overall performance, even if some would have preferred larger server options, additional visualization toolkits, and the possibility to use a personal public Binder to run notebooks from. The overall improvement that was mentioned concerns the possibility to deploy a Dask worker not only locally but also across several infrastructures, allowing access to a distributed environment deployed on multiple clusters related on Kubernetes, thus improving computing and parallel processing.

The UC has also explored links with other national or European projects, such as Blue Cloud⁶⁰ and PHIDIAS⁶¹, regarding the technical implementation and challenges of data access and processing in Earth system communities, and possible technical choices for data synchronization (iRODS), data discovery (test of PHIDIAS common metadata model), and processing (D4Science facilities). The achievements of the UC and the experience gained throughout the project will serve as basis for different projects facing the same challenges such as the French Equipex+ PIA3 project GAÏA DATA⁶² and the HE-funded project FAIR-EASE⁶³ that will reuse part of the UC's results in a more operational context.

⁵⁵ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/use-cases/agile-fair-data-environment-and-earth-system-communities>

⁵⁶ Vernet, Marine, Drago, Federico, & Savini, Gianluca. (2022). EOSC-Pillar Use case 2 - Agile FAIR data for environment and Earth system communities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6725227>

⁵⁷ Vernet, Marine, Harscoat, Valérie, Queric, Antoine, Maudire, Gilbert, Antonio, Fabrizio, Kulüke, Marco, Kindermann, Stephan, Sudre, Joël, Pierkot, Christelle, Jourdain, Cédric, & Donvito, Giacinto. (2022). EOSCPillar4EarthScience: a FAIR-enabled Virtual Data Analysis Platform for Environment and Earth System communities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7194818>

⁵⁸ https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCPillarTrainingAndSupport/eoscpillar4earthscience_vre_-_quick_start

⁵⁹ Antonio Fabrizio, Vernet Marine, Kulüke Marco, Sudre Joël, Harscoat Valérie, Quéric Antoine, Maudire Gilbert & Kindermann Stephan (2022). EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE – Quick Start. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7128695>

⁶⁰ EU-funded project : <https://blue-cloud.org/>

⁶¹ EU-funded project financed by INEA and CEF: <https://www.phidias-hpc.eu/press-clipping/phidias-overview-2>

⁶² <http://gaia-data.org/>

⁶³ <https://fairease.eu/>

2.3 UC6.3: “Integration of Data repositories into EOSC based on communities’ approaches”

2.3.1 The UC description

Global objectives

The goal of the UC 6.3 was to explore the current limitations and provide solutions to address long term preservation, re-usability and reproducibility of data published in repositories.

The UC demonstrators used the Dataverse project⁶⁴, a powerful research data repository software with an increasing use among various communities with 91 declared installation⁶⁵ to this date. This is also the software used by France’s new national research data repository Recherche Data Gouv⁶⁶.

The UC approach was based on scientific needs identified in the Agri-food sector⁶⁷, but with partners and tools from other communities, in order to provide generic solutions that could be applied to other scientific domains.

High-level overview

As part of this UC, we focused on the following items:

- **Data Preservation**, producing:
 - An archiving workflow from Dataverse based repositories to Vitam⁶⁸ and B2SAFE⁶⁹.
- **Data analysis in the cloud**, producing:
 - An OpenStack⁷⁰ instance and Kubernetes⁷¹ cluster provisioning over INRAE’s and France Grille’s infrastructures
 - On demand computing environments for Jupyter⁷², Renku⁷³, Binder⁷⁴ and Rshiny⁷⁵.
 - A connector between Dataverse based repositories and JupyterHub⁷⁶ platform.
- **Data discoverability in data catalogs**, producing:
 - A connector between Dataverse based repositories and Fraunhofer material sciences marketplace⁷⁷.
 - Dataverse based repository data harvesting in the Federated FAIR Data Space⁷⁸ in conjunction with WP5.
- **Data integration in Virtual Research Environments (VRE)**, producing:
 - A connector between Dataverse based repositories and a project deployed D4Science Virtual Research Environment⁷⁹.
 - An improvement to D4Science to use external computing platforms.

Implementation details

Since M24 of the project there has been a significant progress in several items of the UC. Only the demonstrators that either were published or received improvement are presented below, for more

⁶⁴ <https://dataverse.org/>

⁶⁵ ‘The Dataverse Project - Dataverse.Org’. Accessed 25 November 2022. <https://dataverse.org/home>

⁶⁶ <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en/page/a-multidisciplinary-repository>

⁶⁷ <https://repository.eosc-pillar.eu/index.php/s/fWNGnbzmpcY5ZJ3>

⁶⁸ <https://github.com/ProgrammeVitam/vitam>

⁶⁹ <https://www.eudat.eu/b2safe>

⁷⁰ <https://www.openstack.org/>

⁷¹ <https://kubernetes.io/>

⁷² <https://jupyter.org/>

⁷³ <https://renkulab.io/>

⁷⁴ <https://jupyter.org/binder>

⁷⁵ <https://shiny.rstudio.com/>

⁷⁶ <https://jupyter.org/hub>

⁷⁷ <https://www.the-marketplace-project.eu/en/AbouttheMarketplaceProject.html>

⁷⁸ <https://eosc-pillar.eu/federated-fair-data-space-f2ds>

⁷⁹ <https://ckan-eosc-pillar.d4science.org/>

details or previous productions by the UC, please refer to the deliverable 6.2⁸⁰, the UC fact sheet⁸¹ and the UC poster⁸².

The **Dataverse-JupyterHub Connector** now includes a script to allow the publication of the analysis and the processed data back to the data repository. The source code has been made available at "<https://forgemia.inra.fr/dipso/eosc-pillar/dataverse-jupyterhub-connector>".

The **Archiving workflow** has been completed. We were able to test it on real production data to validate it. The source code has been made available at <https://forgemia.inra.fr/dipso/eosc-pillar/dataverse-vitam-archiving>

Fraunhofer **Marketplace connector** has been released, allowing to import Dataverse datasets or metadata in the marketplace. The source code has been made available at <https://github.com/materials-marketplace/dataverse-app>.

What could be improved or explored in the future?

Software Heritage harvesting of the source codes deposited in Dataverse based repositories which was excluded from the DOA during its revision but is still of interest to the users' community, especially as the workflow for such deposit is being improved by another project (HERMES⁸³). It could therefore be a follow-up collaboration with UC4 member to develop this feature.

Deployments for other platforms as Wholetale⁸⁴ were initially planned but were deemed of too great complexity for the scientific value of these demonstrators as a public instance of the application and a Dataverse connector both already exists.

Other connectors for Binder and Renku, initially planned also resulted in dead ends with technical issues on the platforms' side that couldn't be resolved within the project lifespan. Such demonstrators would still be of interest when these issues will have been resolved. The source code for the Renku connector in its incomplete state has been made available at <https://forgemia.inra.fr/dipso/eosc-pillar/dataverse-renku-connector>.

A joint work with UC 6 on **Galaxy** was proposed during the project to connect this service (see UC 6) to Dataverse based repository but couldn't be added to the UC demonstrators. This connection would be interesting to develop in the future, especially as Inserm (UC6 task leader) has since joined the Recherche Data Gouv infrastructure.

OpenSilex⁸⁵ (ontology-driven Information System for phenotype data) data publication workflow in Dataverse is still in active development. The dataset creation mechanism envisioned within the project scope will be done by M42 and accessible at <https://github.com/OpenSILEX/opensilex>, and the development to enable data transfer will be continued further after the end of the EOSC-Pillar project.

Production release of the JupyterHub and archiving demonstrators is planned for France's national research data repository Recherche Data Gouv after its beta phase ending in 2024.

⁸⁰ Rizzo, Alessandro, Pierkot, Christelle, Vernet, Marine, Sudre, Joël, von Hartrott, Philipp, & Berberi, Lisana. (2022). EOSC-Pillar D6.2 - Demonstrators and success stories from the use cases. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/record/6541565>

⁸¹ Drago, Federico, & Savini, Gianluca. (2022). EOSC-Pillar Use case 3 - Integration of data repositories into EOSC based on communities approaches. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6725546>

⁸² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7228219>

⁸³ <https://project.software-metadata.pub/>

⁸⁴ <https://wholetale.org/>

⁸⁵ <http://opensilex.org/>

2.3.2 2.3.2 Communities involvement

Presentations, talks and posters during events, workshops and conferences

Event	Date	Description	Link
INRAE webinar	Mar. 2020	Talk “Contributions INRAE à l’intégration des entrepôts de données dans l’EOSC - Le projet EOSC-Pillar”	https://www6.inrae.fr/diapo/Notre-offre-de-services/en-numerique-scientifique/Les-cafes-numeriques
French EOSC Days	Apr. 2022	Talk “Points intéressants d’EOSC-Pillar”	https://eoscfrance2022.sciencesconf.org/397789

A presentation of the JupyterHub connector to the Dataverse community⁸⁶ has been postponed but will also result in a recorded demonstration of the tool, available on DataverseTV⁸⁷.

Online communication and dissemination

The UC 6.3 has worked throughout the project in close collaboration with WP2 to produce online material describing the Use case and its results, namely:

- Use case page on EOSC-Pillar website⁸⁸
- Use case “factsheet”⁸⁹
- A video demonstration⁹⁰
- A poster⁹¹

A technical note on the JupyterHub connector is also being written and will be published to promote the UC demonstrators in an additional scientific communication channel.

Outreach, community involvement and potential use by other communities

All connectors have been developed to interface with standard built-in features of the Dataverse project, allowing their reuse for all Dataverse-based repositories, of any scientific community. Their adoption in the Recherche Data Gouv repository, as a multidisciplinary repository, will allow other communities to use these features.

A hackathon to provide new concrete use cases and get further feedback on the demonstrators is planned in December 2022 with limited number of participants from the UC partners, already reaching further than the Agri-food community.

Another edition of this hackathon, open to a broader audience will be conducted after the project.

National initiatives - France

As aforementioned, the UC data repository became a national repository during the project, therefore the demonstrators produced by the Use Case will contribute to new services and EOSC integration for the data repository component of Recherche Data Gouv⁹², the national research data ecosystem and through it an element of the Second French Plan for Open Science⁹³.

⁸⁶ <https://dataverse.org/community-calls>

⁸⁷ <https://dataverse.org/dataversetv>

⁸⁸ <https://eosc-pillar.eu/use-cases/integration-data-repositories-eosc-based-communities-approaches>

⁸⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7228219>

⁹⁰ <https://youtu.be/iaifHjpj2HgQ>

⁹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7228219>

⁹² <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en/page/about-recherche-data-gouv>

⁹³ <https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/second-national-plan-for-open-science/>

2.4 UC6.4: “Software Source Code Preservation, Reference and Access”

2.4.1 The UC description

Global objectives

The goal of this use case (UC) was to leverage, on the one hand, the experience of Software Heritage and, on the other, the resources and network of EOSC, to design and implement a solution for the preservation of massive collections (target scale: billions of files with links to publications) of software source code integrated into the EOSC ecosystem.

High-level overview

Specifically, as part of this use case we have:

- Developed an API that allows researchers to explicit deposit the source code of research software for archival
- Developed an API that allows to access and retrieve archived software source code
- Standardized a schema of persistent identifiers, called SWHID, that enables referencing billions of archived source code artifacts
- Integrated the above APIs and Services into the EOSC service catalog
- Designed a pilot to fully host a mirror of the Software Heritage archive onto existing EOSC infrastructure

Implementation details

Long term preservation of the Software Heritage Archive is guaranteed by the Software Heritage project itself, but as part of this UC, an additional resiliency layer has been designed to keep up to date an additional copy of the archive into the CINES (another EOSC-Pillar project partner) archiving platform Vitam. This additional copy acts as a cold storage backup and is not meant to be used as a live/searchable copy of the archive but provides a precious disaster recovery backup in case of emergency.

Targeted users

This use case targets any scientific community that make use of software in their research activity (which, nowadays, is almost all scientific communities).

At individual level:

- a researcher can ensure a software source code involved in the production of a paper is archived by Software Heritage, and
- he/she is able to precisely and intrinsically identify any piece of source code using a SWHID identifier, and
- she/he able to retrieve any piece of code from the Software Heritage Archive from the SWHID, even if the original origin for this code (original git repository, forge, etc.) is not available any more.

At community/institution level:

- an institution can deposit source code software it produces, with a curated process and with associated metadata, directly into the Software Heritage Archive or via associated infrastructure such as HAL, and
- have this software automatically pushed in the Software Heritage Archive, and get resulting SWHID for identification and citation purpose.

Entry points

The main web application used to interact with the archive as a user is located at <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/>

The public API used to interact with the archive as a developer is located at <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/api/1/>

Provided services

Searching the Software Heritage Archive for source code of interest by project metadata or original hosting is possible interactively on the web starting at <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/browse/search/> and programmatically via API at <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/api/1/origin/search/doc/>.

Browsing the Software Heritage Archive is possible using the web app on <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/>. Navigating the underlying Software Heritage graph structure is available via the public API on <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/api/1/>.

Users can ask the Software Heritage Archive to take a snapshot of a publicly available source code repository (git, mercurial or subversion) using the **Save Code Now** service at <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/save/>. A corresponding API entry point is also available.

Deposit an archive file (zip, tar) containing source code and a codemeta metadata description of the deposited source code is available at <https://deposit.softwareheritage.org/>. This service is only available as an API (based on SWORD) but a command line interface tool is provided to help using this API. This service is only available to some authenticated users.

Retrieve archived software source code is possible navigating the Software Heritage Archive and using the Vault service at <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/browse/vault/>. This Vault service is responsible for gathering all the files and content from the Software Heritage Archive and build a zip file ready for the user to download. It is possible to download a single file, a complete directory (as a zip file) or a full git history.

SWHID (persistent and intrinsic identifier) of any source code artifact stored in the Software Heritage Archive can be obtained interactively while navigating the archive. The web application allows to craft either Core SWHID (identifier of the artifact only, without qualifiers) or Extended SWHID (with qualifiers, like the Origin the artifact comes from, or a fragment qualifier to identify only a portion of a source code file, e.g. a specific function or class). Computing locally the SWHID of a source code artifact is possible either using custom code implementing the [SWHID public specifications](#), or using the [command line interface tool](#) provided by Software Heritage.

Tutorial — search, navigation, and SWHID retrieval

Search & navigate

The screenshot shows the 'Search archived software' interface. At the top, there are navigation links: Home, Development, Documentation, Donate, and login. Below the navigation is a search bar with the text 'nakala' and a search icon. There are three filter options: 'only show origins visited at least once' (checked), 'filter out origins with no archived content' (checked), and 'search in metadata (instead of URL)' (unchecked). A 'visit type' dropdown menu is set to 'any'. Below the filters is a table of search results.

Origin type	Origin url	Archiving status
git	https://github.com/NakalanziJacklyn/ToDoListApp	✓ Archived
git	https://github.com/NakalanziJacklyn/Hs_Website	✓ Archived
svn	http://mashup-aparna-seth2-nakalachi.googlecode.com/svn/	✓ Archived
git	https://gitlab.huma-num.fr/nakala-tools/nakanav	✓ Archived
git	https://github.com/ayumu838/nakalabstudy	✓ Archived
git	https://github.com/SiahL/nakala	✓ Archived
git	https://github.com/NakalanziJacklyn/hero_data	✓ Archived
git	https://github.com/kyfr59/nakala-export	✓ Archived

Figure 9: Example of results for the query "nakala"; returns a list of projects which name (actually project URL) involves the "nakala" word.

Figure 10: Browsing page for a project archived by Software Heritage; here, the dfih-tools project from the [Huma-Num gitlab repository](https://gitlab.huma-num.fr/eurhisfirm/). The main navigation page for a project shows the content (list of files and directories) of the project (for the latest gathered revision) as well as the content of the README file, if any. The user can browse the directory tree for the selected branch, can browse the git history, download the displayed directory (as a zip file), or get the SWHID for the displayed object.

Obtain a SWHID

Figure 11: Every displayed object, when browsing the Software Heritage Archive, has a permanent and unique identifier, the [SWHID](#), that can be displayed via the "Permalink" tool.

Download a copy of the code

Figure 12: When the displayed object is a Directory or a Revision, it's possible to download it using the "Download" tool button. Internally, the service responsible for gathering all the software artifacts and create a zip file ready to download is the Vault.

2.4.2 Technical links with EOSC and other use cases

- The Software Heritage Archive and all the above services have been enrolled into the [EOSC service catalog](#).
- The authentication service of the Software Heritage Archive has been linked with KIT Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) as part of the WP7 effort to help EOSC partners interested in integrating Software Heritage services in their platform.
- Use case 6.2 (Agile FAIR data for environment and earth system communities): interest in integrating Software Heritage into the Pangeo community platform
- Use case 6.3 (Integration of data repositories into EOSC based on communities approaches): interest into integrating the Dataverse platform into the Software Heritage archive, similarly to what has been already done (independently from EOSC-Pillar) for the Zenodo/Invenio RDM platform
- Use case 6.5 (FAIR principles in data life-cycles for Humanities) expressed interest into integrating Software Heritage into Nakala (esp. add support in Nakala to reference software source code using SWHID) in the future.

2.4.3 Communities involvement

As part of the work conducted for this Use case we have participated in the activities of many national, European, and worldwide international communities, projects, and initiatives. The most notable ones were:

Worldwide communities

- [RDA](#) Software Source Code interest group (ongoing)
 - FAIR4RS (joint work with FORCE11 and ReSA)
 - Software Identification working group (joint work with FORCE11)
- [FORCE11](#)
 - Software Citation Implementation working group

- [ReSA](#) Research Software Alliance

European projects and initiatives

- [FAIRsFAIR](#) (2019-2022)
- [FAIR IMPACT](#) (2022-2025)
- [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#) (2022-2025); implementation of the recommendations of the SIRS report (identification of subjects to be pushed to plan calls for funding to fill the gaps)
- [EOSC SIRS report](#)
- [EOSC TF](#) Infrastructures for quality software

National (French) initiatives

- HAL / Software deposit working group
- Inria Software Citation WG
- MESR (French Ministry of Higher Education and Research): CoSO (national open science committee)
- National plan for Research Software - PNSO2

2.5 UC6.5: “FAIR principles in data life-cycle for humanities”

2.5.1 The UC description

Initial objectives and methodology

In the context of the task 6.5 of EOSC-PILLAR project (<https://www.eosc-pillar.eu>), several use cases in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) had been discussed, but the main one consisted in a Proof of Concept of creating a link between data and publications. More precisely, it has been undertaken to initiate a collaboration to link the French open archive HAL, more specifically the part restricted to SSH resources (<https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr>), and NAKALA (<https://www.nakala.fr>), the French repository dedicated to SSH and supported by the French research infrastructure Huma-Num (<https://www.huma-num.fr>).

In order to establish this kind of link, several technical and methodological aspects had to be taken into account. We also considered the different types of potential scenarios in order to build a theoretical workflow and all the necessary prerequisites (eg. To be able to create a relationship, the user must have an account in HAL and be the owner of the scientific document deposited in HAL for which he is creating a relationship, but it is not necessary for the user to have rights to the data in NAKALA).

We discussed it during the first year of the project and this led to the technical specifications and choices detailed in MS26 (<https://zenodo.org/record/5553857>) and D6.2 (<https://zenodo.org/record/6541565>) and summarized by the following schema.

Figure 13: Technical specifications

Main results and perspectives

The implementation of the technical choices in terms of relationships between HAL publications and data stored in NAKALA has been done on both platforms to integrate the creation of two-way links. This led to a choice of a communication tool: Mercure in that case (<https://www.ietf.org/archive/id/draft-dunglas-mercure-07.html>), hosted by Huma-Num. During M24 to M32, the final step that consisted in installing a Mercure instance on Huma-Num servers was to redefine the interfaces in order to display the links in both platforms: in HAL, the relationship is expressed on the page describing a publication and in NAKALA additional metadata are added on the data landing page.

The implementation is now effective on both test platforms and so we have some perspective on the various problems that may arise.

If the main highlight remains the implementation of the POC between the HAL and NAKALA repositories (in particular, the synchronization and exposition of relationships within both repositories), various extensions are envisaged in the framework of future collaborations and projects at the national level. One of them will consist, if possible, in allowing the simultaneous deposit of publications and data in the same repository, HAL, and then transferring the data into Nakala, creating the relationship between the two repositories automatically, on the model of what has already been developed in HAL for software codes, in partnership with the Software Heritage repository. It is also conceivable, by means of a survey of users of the two data repositories, to deepen the bi-directional character of the "simple" link initially created, as well as its visualization. For various reasons, usually related to technical difficulties, there was not enough time to conduct this kind of usability survey with the communities involved but work on this topic will continue in another setting (see further in the text).

A study has been also initiated about the use of two different tools B2Note (<https://www.eudat.eu/catalogue/B2NOTE>) and SCHOLIX (Scholexplorer - <https://scholexplorer.openaire.eu>) in order to disseminate the relationships created between HAL publications and NAKALA data: this was not implemented but SCHOLIX seems to be the more suitable for that purpose and the reflexion initiated surely will be useful for other initiatives.

Lastly, the realization of this POC has committed us to a regular and constructive dialogue between our two national research infrastructures. Beyond the technical aspects on which we worked and on which we agreed, this dialogue was an undeniable added-value for our two infrastructures to consider future collaborations. We would like to insist on this point which appears to us as one of the notable successes achieved thanks to the EOSC-Pillar project, in the exact vein of its objectives.

2.5.2 Additional UC and its linkages with other WPs

In the context of T6.5, we also identified an interesting "sub-UC" to develop, and which would allow us to use other resources of the EOSC-Pillar project, in particular that of WP7, and to bring together two French national infrastructures from different scientific fields (SSH and ecology, physiology and ethology, chemistry and subatomic physics). The links developed with other WPs of the project were therefore essentially developed via this additional use-case entitled "Share and analyse LIDAR data as a service". It is also a proof of concept based on an ERC project called Archeoscape.

The Archeoscape project

This project is a 5 years (2020-2025) research initiative funded under the ERC Consolidator Grant Scheme and led by M. Damian Evans. It follows the previous work of the Greater Angkor Project and the two LIDAR initiatives in Cambodia in 2012 and 2015 (CALI ERC Program 2015-2020). The main goal

of this project is to tackle the core problems that currently constrain the 'lidar revolution' in archaeology: the use of a new generation of lidar technologies to greatly expand coverage in South-east Asia, home to many of the most important and understudied rainforest landscapes.

The most visible result of this work will be the creation of a consistent, comparable datasets of human impacts on the Earth's surface, with a view to understanding trajectories of innovation and complexity in the tropical world from the deep past to the present.

In order to promote open data and collaborative work on huge lidar datasets, the project aims to develop open access frameworks and infrastructures for aggregating, sharing and collaborating on lidar datasets. It will build on recent advances in artificial intelligence to develop generic models for automation and analysis, in order to move beyond localized, culturally-specific lidar applications open to all researchers.

Challenges and requirements: why was the EOSC-PILLAR ecosystem necessary?

The project funds the data acquisition systems and its specific development needs, but relies on national infrastructures for:

- Data storage.
- Data preservation (90 TB of raw lidar data).
- Hosting a virtual research environment for offering services around these data.
- Providing resources for deep learning analysis.

To provide the data and the analysis framework to a larger community, the current provided resources at the beginning of EOSC-Pillar were not sufficient. It has been decided to use other resources, made available through this project, to be able to scale and answer the user's needs.

The optimal use of EOSC-Pillar resources involves overcoming several challenges:

- Technical challenges of Lidar data sharing and processing: the high-performance resources needed for serving deep learning on a huge dataset "as a service" depends on resource availability for scaling. Ideally a calculation job should start as soon as a user asks for it from a web platform but using classical high-performance computing platform implies the submission of a job to a scheduler, launching it once the resources are available. Using new kind of resources, like GPU as a service, may solve this kind of issue, but requires many developments.
- Prefiguring new services at European level, "from scratch" and not already funded. It relates to sustainability, while these rules are not yet defined for EOSC.
- Supporting a wider research community needs access to larger computing facilities to obtain the necessary elasticity.
- Interoperability between the EOSC-Pillar services and larger facilities is a requirement.

Achievements

In order to meet the technical challenges, a work plan was set up at the end of 2021 with the help of WP7. First of all, the technical specifications were drawn up and validated by the various stakeholders. At the same time, a fixed-term contract was recruited to accompany us for a period of six months on this project.

The technical specifications define two main infrastructures:

- An association of single-site infrastructures for hosting the services but using technologies capable of scaling up. This infrastructure is designed to host the POC and will run for the

demonstration on big national infrastructures in the spirit of the EOSC-Pillar project (Huma-Num for storage, data quality and maybe collaborative tools, and the SCIGNE platform for calculating and AI).

- A European-wide distributed infrastructure capable of being deployed through EOSC for the production, using both EOSC thematic services and EGI facilities.

We made sure that the two infrastructures were interoperable, so that the transition between the two would be as transparent as possible. Regarding the technical implementation, it was decided to work with proven and interoperable technologies:

- A Cloud infrastructure based on OpenStack for the deployment of the servers (Web, AI). This choice will also allow the solution to be deployed on the EGI European federated cloud.
- A service orchestration system based on Kubernetes, a tool that guarantees both the elasticity of the solution and the shared use of GPU resources for deep learning.
- The use of Terraform and Ansible to create an Infrastructure as a Code, in order to facilitate the daily management, to favor the maintainability and to allow the redeployment on other infrastructures.

Once the specifications were validated by all the partners, the different steps leading to a POC were carried out:

- Provision of hardware resources on the SCIGNE Cloud platform.
- Setting up the centralized deployment system based on Terraform and Ansible to deploy and configure the POC.
- Development of the Infrastructure as Code to deploy the POC. This was quite challenging, as the infrastructure incorporates GPUs that need to be made available to the user interface through Kubernetes.
- Additional developments have been done, including the use of Helm and many infrastructure tests.
- The POC has been released. It is based on a GPU-Enabled Jupyter notebook. This notebook is accessible to all users of this use-case and permits to test the Relief Visualization Toolbox (RVT, <https://iaps.zrc-sazu.si/en/rvt>) for LIDAR image analysis in a Cloud environment.
- For reasons of security and processing speed, a storage space of 100 TB was also reserved on the iRODS service of France Grilles, co-located with the Cloud Computing service for data processing. The iRODS system is directly accessible through the Jupyter Notebook thanks to the available driver.

Current development and perspectives

RVT is more than just a toolbox and provides a complete environment for LIDAR data analysis. The full RVT suite is unfortunately not working in a containerized environment, as needed for a full Kubernetes-based deployment. So, before switching to the production environment, it is necessary to work on the structure of RVT to make it compatible with the Kubernetes system. This work has already started and is currently in progress and led by the RVT software editor.

Once the new RVT release is available, it will be deployed on a larger infrastructure for production. To do this, we have already pre-selected a set of providers capable of meeting our needs in the EOSC catalog. We will contact them as soon as the software stack is available to test the production infrastructure deployment. In parallel, we have to work on the sustainability model of the service, as the system requires regular maintenance, both on functional and security points, and implies a human cost associated with technical resource cost. This work is intertwined with the ongoing work on the definition of the EOSC business model. It will be pursued in the framework of the EOSC-Pillar collaboration between the Huma-Num infrastructure and the IHPC (<https://iphc.cnrs.fr/en/home/>).

2.5.3 Communities involvement

First of all, at the request of the WP2 of the project, we worked on a video presentation of the Nakala-HAL POC (main UC), currently published on the YouTube Channel of the EOSC-Pillar project (<https://youtu.be/DxZ8HOQ0vHU>), integrated on the web page description of the use case on EOSC-Pillar website (<https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/use-cases/fair-principles-data-life-cycles-humanities>). We have presented it in several meetings of the WP6 since April 2021.

In order to raise attention of French research communities, above all SSH, we also presented it internally within the network of Huma-Num Consortia and Stakeholders, as it was published in our social networks and web site (<https://www.huma-num.fr/projets/#pillar>). We will also publish a report of such activities carried out within the EOSC-Pillar project in the research blog of Huma-Num (<https://humanum.hypotheses.org/>) by the end of the year, as well as the CCSD on their own blog (<https://www.ccsd.cnrs.fr/blog/>).

To discuss it in a broader scope, we presented a poster (<https://zenodo.org/record/7156780>) during the final event of EOSC-Pillar on the 26th of October and we submitted a long paper to DH2023 Conference <https://dh2023.adho.org/> (paper currently under review) which will allow to be even more inclusive in terms of targeted audience. Indeed, one of the goals of this POC, as an experiment, was to address the fundamental questions mentioned above. This work will continue in the context of a national project, HALIANCE, by taking into account the evolution of the French national context, for instance the development of a national repository (<https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/>).

2.6 UC6.6: “Exploring reference data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics”

2.6.1 The UC description

Global objectives

Galaxy⁹⁴ is one of the best-known workflow management systems for bioinformatics, aiming to make computational biology accessible to research scientists that do not have computer programming or systems administration experience.

How can scientists connect this powerful tool seamlessly with many data sources? How can they do so in a coherent way using different instances of Galaxy? Can they run it locally or on a secured infrastructure that handles patient data? Can they compare the results of those different scenarios? Those are the main questions this use-case wants to address.

Building on top of existing French and Italian national services, the use-case will produce guidelines and best practices, and implement a service prototype based on different scientific scenarios in order to:

- Allow access to reference data from different Galaxy deployments within the EOSC
- Facilitate the deployment of Galaxy instances close to the data
- Provide coherency between different existing Galaxy deployments
- Ensure health data security requirements are met throughout the process

Challenges addressed

Galaxy is a widely used tool and comes in many flavours. One of the first challenges to address is the reproducibility and coherency of the different deployments to ensure that data analysis workflows produce the same results whatever the instance used. This means technical work within Galaxy itself, but also a global reflection on how to connect different data sources to Galaxy in a simple and coherent way.

Another challenge is the need to conform to data protection regulations concerning health personal data, by deploying Galaxy in a private, secured environment while still ensuring the data analysis workflow remains similar to its public counterpart.

Finally, we must find a way of providing access to the service to all users within the EOSC community through roles management and by integrating it into a global authentication framework.

Activities carried out throughout the EOSC-Pillar project

Defining generic usage scenarios

T6.6 team has defined 4 theoretical scenarios based on user stories. These are:

- **Scenario 1: Public Galaxy instance(s).** A user needs to implement a Galaxy workflow that requires input data from institutional repositories (such as Inserm repository) or data from a public database. This can be done using a Galaxy public server, in our prototype hosted on an EOSC-Pillar partner infrastructure (INFN) and using the EOSC-Pillar Federated FAIR dataspace (FFDS) for searching and accessing required input data. Finally, output data are moved to an institutional repo/storage.
- **Scenario 2: Close-to-the-data deployment.** A user needs to perform analysis on big files (and/or many files) through an I/O intensive workflow, but he doesn't want to, or it is not possible to, upload data on a public Galaxy instance. He/She obtains from the FFDS needed information about data location and nearest infrastructures. He/She can easily deploy a private Galaxy instance, through Laniakea, on an infrastructure close to the data. This Galaxy

⁹⁴ The Galaxy Community, The Galaxy platform for accessible, reproducible and collaborative biomedical analyses: 2022 update, Nucleic Acids Research, Volume 50, Issue W1, 5 July 2022, Pages W345–W351, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac247>

instance has the same features than the central one, therefore the same workflow can be used. Output data are stored locally and referenced in an institutional repository.

- **Scenario 3: Health data with restricted access.** Users need to perform analysis on a dataset with strong legal requirements (personal/health data). As a result, this dataset can only be accessed from a secured “bubble”, and there are strong restrictions and procedures for deploying Galaxy in such an environment. They get this information, along with details about access request procedure, from the FFDS. Once they can access the data, they can perform the analysis on a private Galaxy instance, deployed using Laniakea in secured environment. Output data are stored in the perimeter of these secured environment and, if possible, is populated elsewhere and referenced in an institutional repository.
- **Scenario 4: Reproducibility and verification.** User needs to compare workflows and/results obtained through scenarios 1, 2 and 3. For that, he needs to be sure that analyses have been produced through the same workflow, and if there are any difference, be able to identify them. Similarly, he should be able to reproduce results from those scenarios.

Laniakea service improvements (linked with T7.4)

The Laniakea⁹⁵ software framework was improved alongside the application of the three different scenarios and the drafting of the best practices.

In particular, the developments are focused on improving the maintainability of the software framework by reworking the Laniakea Ansible roles, the update of the Laniakea encryption system and the extension of the application pool.

Ansible⁹⁶ is an automation engine, widely used on Cloud environments, able to automate the deployment of complex services, performing a list of tasks grouped in a predefined directory structure, named “Ansible role”. The Laniakea Live system exploits multiple custom Ansible roles, to install and configure Galaxy and its tools on a Virtual Machine. The downside of this solution is that the Ansible roles need to be continuously updated to match the new Galaxy releases. Therefore, the system has been reworked by integrating the official Galaxy Project Ansible roles, suggested also by “the best practices to deploy Galaxy” specified in the subtask 6.6.1, which aims at the rationalization of the Ansible roles for the deployment of Galaxy. This will allow for faster updates (the Galaxy Project roles are updated at the same time as the release of a new version of Galaxy), making it easier to maintain the Laniakea framework. Also, the express deployment system has been reworked, using for the creation of the Galaxy image the same official Ansible roles, made available by the Galaxy community.

Working in vision of the scenario 3, the Laniakea management of sensitive data has been improved by redesigning the system for volumes encryption implemented in Laniakea V.2.0.0.

The Laniakea encryption module has been completely reworked to port the system, previously developed in Python 2 and bash, to Python 3 and make the encryption process simpler and more linear to perform and maintain. All the components needed to encrypt the volume, mount it, and the API required for controlling the encryption process through the Laniakea dashboard were implemented and made available through the development of a Python package called PyLUKS⁹⁷, installable using pip. The new volume encryption strategy has been generalized and can now be applied also to applications other than Galaxy, and can be used with all the present and future applications supported by Laniakea.

⁹⁵ Marco Antonio Tangaro, Giacinto Donvito, Marica Antonacci, Matteo Chiara, Pietro Mandreoli, Graziano Pesole, Federico Zambelli, Laniakea: an open solution to provide Galaxy “on-demand” instances over heterogeneous cloud infrastructures, GigaScience, Volume 9, Issue 4, April 2020, g1aa033, <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/g1aa033>

⁹⁶ <https://www.ansible.com/>

⁹⁷ <https://pypi.org/project/pyluks/>

This update provides a more manageable solution for storage encryption and its management, which has been proven to be useful for data protection.

The update has been presented at the WALS conference which is ICWE conference on web applications for life sciences⁹⁸.

The Laniakea applications portfolio has been extended, adding new standalone applications widely used in the bioinformatics field, whose aim is to facilitate and make reproducible the data analysis workflow. Three new applications have been integrated in the Laniakea framework: Rstudio-server⁹⁹, JupyterHub¹⁰⁰ and IRIDA¹⁰¹. Each one of those applications has been ported into the system developing the corresponding Ansible roles required for the live deployment, the creation of a cloud image hosting the software, and to set specific configuration adjustments during the deployment phase.

This expansion of the application pool has made Laniakea's management and update more complex for this reason we have decided, in the context of the Wp7.4 to implement for Laniakea a Continuous Integration and Delivery (CI/CD) development approach. To apply this approach, we have developed a CI/CD system based on Jenkins. The system has been populated with different pipelines with two main focuses: simplifying the maintenance of the Laniakea "express" applications (the deployment type based on a pre-configured VM containing all the software packages needed for its functioning), and to test both the system and all the applications periodically to timely identify any possible issue introduced during the development.

Studying health data handling specific aspects

Scenario 3 described above highlights the need to define specific requirements linked to the manipulation of sensitive data (patient data and personal information). Legal and ethical requirements are needed in order to comply with the legal framework and to remove obstacles to data sharing and interoperability, according to the FAIR and Open Science principles. The research activities take into account the differences between the French Legal Order and the Italian Legal Order on this topic, in the transnational context.

In the context of T6.6, a complete report of this work ("Legal Framework for the use and re-use of health data for scientific purposes") has been produced and is available online¹⁰².

This document aims to:

- define the Legal Framework for the use and re-use of health data for scientific purposes;
- outline the most important gap deriving from the differences between National laws concerning the processing of health data and the possible solution;
- suggest a guide for researchers involved in this scenario

Conceiving a concrete application to hCNV detection as a concrete implementation of scenario 1

Most human cells divide by mitosis, where one parent cell divides to produce two daughter cells. Just before a cell divides it makes a copy of its own DNA, but this copy may not have the same gene sequence as the parent DNA. One gene may for example be copied twice into the new DNA or not copied at all. This phenomenon is called Copy Number Variation (CNV).

It is thought that these Copy Number Variations are vital for evolution, but they also play important roles in disease. Despite the fact that Copy Number Variations are the most prevalent genetic mutation

⁹⁸ <https://icwe2022.webengineering.org/wals2022/>

⁹⁹ <https://www.rstudio.com/products/rstudio/download-server/>

¹⁰⁰ <https://jupyter.org/hub>

¹⁰¹ <https://irida.ca/>

¹⁰² Nadina Foggetti, Giacinto Donvito, & Marco Antonio Tangaro. (2022). Legal Framework for the use and re-use of health data for scientific purposes (Final). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334878>

type, identifying and interpreting them is still a major challenge (for more information, see the Elixir hCNV community web page¹⁰³).

The ELIXIR hCNV Community aim to implement processes to make the detection, annotation and interpretation of these variations easier. One of the tasks that the community is working on is the benchmarking of different CNV callers, which are the tools used to detect CNV.

Through its *Genome in a Bottle* programme¹⁰⁴, The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) publishes reference hCNV data. To benchmark different tools, the idea is to launch a CNV detection workflow using a given caller on a reference sample provided by the NIST, and then compare obtained result to the gold standard corresponding to that sample to evaluate the efficiency/quality of used caller.

To avoid biases and optimise the benchmarking, we need to ensure that all benchmarks run in a similar environment, and that used workflows are as independent from the underlying infrastructure as possible. We also want to ensure that obtained results are still relevant if we launch real studies, using other data sources than reference data.

This is a concrete example of a real scientific challenge that can match our different theoretical scenarios. A complete description of this concrete application will be provided in UC6 final report, to be produced and published by the end of 2022.

2.6.2 Communities involvement

Presentations, talks and posters on UC6 during events, workshops and conferences

Event	Date	Description	Link
French EOSC Days at CNRS	Jan. 2020	Short presentation and contribution to the global discussion	https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/eosc-pillar-eosc-day-cnrs-paris
EOSC-hub week	May 2020	Short talk	https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/eosc-hub-week-2020
Galaxy Community Conference 2021	Jul. 2021	talk: Marco Antonio Tangaro, Giacinto Donvito, Marica Antonacci, Matteo Chiara, Pietro Mandreoli et al. "Laniakea - Update 2021". F1000Research 2021, 10:636 (slides)	https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1118635.1
PhD workshop UNIMI	Oct. 2021	Poster: Pietro Mandreoli, Marco Antonio Tangaro et al "Laniakea: Shaping and Developing a Cloud-based bioinformatic platform" PhD Workshop 2021 UNIMI, 7-8 October 2021	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6206807
JCAD2021	Dec. 2021	Poster: Sanaa, Yosra, Mathieu, Gilles, et al. (2021). Exploring reference data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5764786
WALS2022	Jul. 2022	Talk : Marco Antonio Tangaro, Marica Antonacci, Pietro Mandreoli, Daniele Colombo, Nadina Foggetti, Giacinto Donvito, Graziano Pesole, Federico Zambelli "The Laniakea Dashboard and storage encryption components: a foundation for developing on-demand	https://icwe2022.webengineering.org/wals2022/

¹⁰³ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/hcnv>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.nist.gov/programs-projects/genome-bottle>

		cloud services for Life Science”	
EGI2022	Sep. 2022	Poster: Sanaa, Yosra, Belhaj Salem, Marwa, Mathieu, Gilles, et al. (2022). Exploring reference data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051283
JCAD2022	Oct. 2022	Talk : Gilles Mathieu, Marwa Belhaj Salem : Retour d'expérience sur le développement d'un cas d'usage en bioinformatique au sein du projet EOSC-Pillar	https://jcad2022.sciencesconf.org/

Online communication and dissemination

T6.6 has worked throughout the project in close collaboration with WP2 to produce online material describing the Use case and its results, namely:

- Use case page on EOSC-Pillar website¹⁰⁵
- Use case “factsheet”¹⁰⁶
- A video demonstration¹⁰⁷

Outreach, community involvement and potential use by other communities

While building our Use case, we had extensive contacts with French representatives of the Elixir hCNV community, as described above. This is not something that was foreseen at the beginning of the project and can be considered an outreach activity.

This allowed one of T6.6 members, Yosra Sanaa, to contribute in September 2020 to Elixir Europe Biohackaton¹⁰⁸.

In parallel, work done around Galaxy as part of T6.6 has led to consider a collaboration with the EOSC-Life project¹⁰⁹, which resulted in a signed collaboration agreement between EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Life in August 2022.

Both projects are collaborating to provide on-demand Galaxy instances, and beyond, in isolated cloud environments, accessible only through virtual VPN by users. This, together with the on-demand Storage Encryption already in place, would provide the possibility to deploy secure instances suitable for sensitive data analysis. Being Laniakea among the EOSC-Life WP7 managed services, these improvements will be available to both communities.

While UC6 was designed based on the needs of the bioinformatics community, the theoretical scenarios, practical scientific scenario, service prototypes and implementation reports produced as part of this use case can be extended to other communities.

Galaxy is widely used in other disciplines ranging from agricultural and food to environmental sciences, and UC6 work can be of interest for those communities. Going beyond the tools themselves, lessons learned from building a data usage scenario on top of EOSC-Pillar services can translate to a wide range of solutions where the challenges are the same, i.e., link source and reference data to computational and analysis tools in a coherent way.

¹⁰⁵ <https://eosc-pillar.eu/use-cases/exploring-reference-data-through-existing-computing-services-bioinformatics-community>

¹⁰⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6726022>

¹⁰⁷ <https://youtu.be/WZey8XrCp1l>

¹⁰⁸ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/BioHackathon-projects-2020/tree/master/projects/7>

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

2.7 UC6.7: “Suitable data formats for seismological Big-data provisioning via web services”

2.7.1 The UC description

Within the seismological community, the last decades have been characterised by large amount of new additional conventional seismic stations becoming available. But now, there are some game-changing technologies under development. This includes deployments consisting of huge numbers of easy-to-install geophones (called “Large-N”); cheap sensors (e.g. MEMs accelerometers) used by mobile devices as well as for infrastructure monitoring; and fibre-optic based technologies (known as DAS), that are each starting to show their great potential in providing quality data with a wide spectrum of applications ranging from Tsunami early warning to Infrastructure monitoring. Despite that, data quality and resolution of these different types of new datasets are different, they have in common the potential to produce large volumes of data in a very short period of time due to both the extremely dense spatial and temporal resolutions.

This considerable increase in the data generation is very challenging for all seismological data centres hosting data, because there is no clear idea how this could be managed by our standard data provisioning systems, which are very stable and mature, but have never faced the need to support an on-the-fly conversion of a big volume of data from proprietary to standard formats.

Large-N deployments and the new DAS systems can generate tens to hundreds of terabytes of data at a small fraction of the cost of using traditional seismometers and geophones for equivalent data volumes. As the price of collecting data becomes drastically cheaper, a corresponding and dramatic increase in the volume of data being collected provides a potential scientific bonanza. However, storing these data in perpetuity is a significant and daunting challenge, as is delivering datasets exceeding a few tens of terabytes. High-performance/ high-throughput computational resources (HPC/HTC) are increasingly necessary to process these data and these resources are not typically provided by the repositories, nor are they co-located with the repositories.

Several Large-N experiments have been already carried out in seismology and archived at some seismological data centres using the actual standards. Data from these experiments are currently distributed via standard FDSN services but with some limitations due to the fast-growing number of experiments as well as additional DAS data being produced in the last couple of years.

Activities carried out throughout the EOSC-Pillar project

One of the main outcomes of this task, is the possibility to be a blueprint for the community. Some of our first results were published in a high-impact-factor journal (SRL), presenting the challenges for the community regarding these new data types (Quinteros et al., 2021). We briefly summarize what has been published in the article, but more details can be found in the publication.

A survey was conducted on selected and self-identified large data users. We classified them in three different categories of data volume: small (1-9 TB), medium (10-50 TB), and large (50+ TB). Some selected results from the survey can be observed in Figure 14.

Both medium and large data users anticipated a use of a variety of data formats, but primarily the miniSEED¹¹⁰ standard and some with HDF5 (PH5¹¹¹ and ASDF¹¹²). However, for users planning to work with 20+ TB, the option of miniSEED reduces considerably in comparison to HDF5-based formats or other less standard formats. A generic HDF5-based solution could have some advantages not only for data centers but also for users needing to process their large datasets in an HPC-friendly format. The

¹¹⁰ <http://ds.iris.edu/ds/nodes/dmc/data/formats/miniseed/>

¹¹¹ <https://github.com/PIC-IRIS/PH5>

¹¹² <http://seismic-data.org/>

main disadvantage for data centers is that HDF5 formatted data cannot currently be streamed on the fly as they are read by the data provisioning systems (Fig. 14, data format).

The data staging factor is closely related to the sustainability of any standard proposed for the data management and provision, due to the impact in the cost of the data hosting. Many medium and large users indicated that they would like to transfer data to their own computer infrastructure or their institutional infrastructure. Many also indicated a preference to deliver data to an HPC center, but only few anticipated relying on commercial cloud providers. Among users working with 20+ TB there seems to be a clear trend in favor of paying for the computational resources for data processing (some dependent on grant allowance).

An unexpected result is that as the size of the datasets grows, users are more conservative with the hosting of their data and refuse to take alternatives like cloud hosting. Two reasons for this are the high cost of this type of storage (if the cost of access is also considered), and the uncertainty and lack of control of the data management. Amazon-like cloud system solutions, which since years has been a hot topic, is considered only by a few users as an option, and only in the case of datasets of less than 20 TB (Fig. 14, data staging).

Figure 14: Different aspects of users' data workflows by size of datasets to be requested. Smaller datasets tend to be requested in miniSEED format, but HDF5-based formats are preferred for larger datasets.

If data centers are expected to increase their archive sizes by at least one order of magnitude (or even more), it might not be feasible to keep all of the data online (Figure 15). Offline (cold) storage should probably be considered inside the data center or provided by external services. This will raise the storage capacity but data would have to be staged on demand, and with limited size and retention time.

Another important topic regarding standardization of any type of datasets is the metadata describing them. There exist comprehensive metadata standards in seismology that are well suited for large nodal data sets or other classical seismic data sets. However, newer, emerging data types such as DAS are not as well handled by these standards. Therefore, one of the most difficult tasks for data centers attempting to identify and implement standard services is to standardize DAS metadata through the definition of new metadata schemas. StationXML, the international standard for seismic metadata, is not a good fit with the technical features of DAS interrogators and the generated datasets. Therefore, we fostered the discussion in different international forums and we are in the process of taking part in the draft of a white paper to be opened to the community.

Figure 15: Evolution of the data archived yearly at each data center (red, black, and blue curves). The error bars on the right show the expected size range of a single dataset for a Large-N (yellow) and a DAS (green) experiment. It can be seen that a single large dataset could be equivalent in size to a whole year of the typical datasets currently being archived (after Quinteros et al., 2021).

The distribution of large data sets (50+ TB) is challenging due to bandwidth constraints. As mentioned previously, one of the main results of the survey we conducted was that the full resolution data is not needed for most studies, particularly for DAS. Instead, a set of products derived from the original data would satisfy most users. The derived data products are often a significantly reduced volume making them more feasible for archiving and distribution by existing data centers and standard protocols. While the derivative products are useful in reducing the burden of transferring bulky data, the need to transfer large volumes is not eliminated for all users.

Another significant challenge is the lack of available services to handle the transmission of large volumes. Not if we would face only a few dataset requests, but the situation is quite different if we consider that each data centre is delivering around 100+ Million datasets per year (Quinteros et al., 2021b).

Despite present initiatives trying to tackle the problem of big seismological datasets and how they can be archived, delivered, and processed, data centers are facing a situation similar to that from the mid-80's. Namely, the amount of data generated was much bigger than the data centers could safely and sustainably archive. At that moment, the temporary solution was to keep only time windows of interest (e.g. waveforms related to an earthquake) and discard the rest of the data after some time. What has been learned from this experience is that discarding data is not the best option to consider, as illustrated by present day research in data mining, new types of seismic signals, and imaging techniques using seismic noise (exactly all data considered not interesting on that time).

At present, the IRIS, GEOFON and RESIF data centers recognize that it is not possible for them to permanently archive on hot storage very large datasets such as DAS due to prohibitive costs of long-term archiving. Therefore, the seismological data centers should explore a strategy for delivering datasets through automatic asynchronous services to designated destinations such as computing facilities where data pre-processing or processing could occur. For very large datasets, a common strategy was developed in this Task to store only standard data products such as spatially and/or temporally down-sampled data, and/or small windows of highly sampled data.

Within this context, **dastools** (Quinteros, 2021), a software package was developed. It includes a set of tools to work with data generated by DAS systems. The **dastools** package provides a library to access and manage DAS datasets generated by systems provided by the two major companies producing this type of instruments (Silixa and Alcatel). This consists of Python classes which are the core of the tools provided. These classes can be imported by the users in their own code and include in it all the flexibility of **dastools**.

dasconv is a tool which lets a user convert and manipulate seismic waveforms in TDMS format (Silixa) and export them into the standard miniSEED. In addition to that, as the DAS data is acquired at a high sampling rate, the conversion can optionally include a decimation of the data in order to create some of the derived products mentioned in the previous section. These products are feasible to be archived and opened to users as any other standard seismological dataset.

Examples

Data acquired from experiments with Silixa systems are usually stored in one folder. Files within this folder have names indicating the experiment and the start time of the waveforms saved. An example of the files generated in a test experiment is shown below.

```
$ ls -l
total 1577352
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:38 default.UTC_20190508_093735.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:38 default.UTC_20190508_093805.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:39 default.UTC_20190508_093835.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:39 default.UTC_20190508_093905.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:40 default.UTC_20190508_093935.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:40 default.UTC_20190508_094005.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:41 default.UTC_20190508_094035.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:41 default.UTC_20190508_094105.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:42 default.UTC_20190508_094135.409.tdms
```

There, 'default' is the name of the experiment and the rest is the start time with the following format:

```
experiment_TZ_YYYYMMDD_HHmms.fff.tdms.
```

dasconv allows the user to convert the data from the supported proprietary formats to the standard miniSEED format.

Some examples of its usage are shown below.

- Export waveforms from channels 800, 802 and 804 starting at 2019-05-08T09:37:35.409000 until 2019-05-08T09:38:05.400000. The waveforms will be exported to miniSEED format after being decimated by a factor of 5 (e.g. from 1000Hz to 200Hz).

```
dasconv -d /home/user/test/ --start "2019-05-08T09:37:35.409000" --end "2019-05-08T09:38:05.400000" default --chstart 800 --chstop 805 --chstep 2
```

- Export waveforms from channels 0 and 1 from the beginning of the measurements until 2019-05-08T09:32:15. The waveforms will be exported to miniSEED format after being decimated by a factor of 5 (e.g. from 1000Hz to 200Hz).

```
dasconv -d /home/user/test/ --endtime "2019-05-08T09:32:15" default --chstart 0 --chstop 1
```

- Export waveforms from channels 0 to 4 from the beginning of the measurements until 2019-05-08T09:32:15. The waveforms will be exported to miniSEED format after being decimated by a factor of 5 (e.g. from 1000Hz to 200Hz).

```
dasconv -d /home/user/test/ --endtime "2019-05-08T09:32:15" default --chstart 0 --chstop 4 --decimate 5
```

dasws is a stand-alone implementation of the FDSN Dataselct web service (international community standard), which is able to serve miniSEED data extracted from a folder with proprietary DAS files. A typical help message showing the usage of **dasws** looks like the following:

```
% dasws -h
usage: dasws [-h] [-mc] [-l {DEBUG,WARNING,INFO,DEBUG}]
tdmsws is an FDSN Dataselct implementation to read TDMS files
optional arguments:
-h, --help            show this help message and exit
-mc, --minimalconfig  Generate a minimal configuration file.
-l {DEBUG,WARNING,INFO,DEBUG}, --log {DEBUG,WARNING,INFO,DEBUG}
                        Increase the verbosity level.
```

The "-mc" switch creates a config file, which should be placed in the same folder as the DAS files. The file includes all needed options and configuration variables which will be read by the software before being able to serve the data.

The user is expected to edit this file and provide the basic information about the DAS experiment before running the service. One can see below a typical config file.

```
[General]
experiment = default
loglevel = INFO

[NSLC]
network = XX
location =
channel = FH1
```

The "experiment" variable refers to the first part of the filenames in the folder. For instance, in the example above, all files will start with "default" and then a timestamp including the timezone (or UTC) will follow (see examples above).

The variables "network", "location" and "channel" will be fixed to define the N.S.L.C code. Only the station will vary and it will always be a number referring to the stream number for the experiment. From the example above, the only valid code would be "XX.00001..FH1", "XX.00002..FH1", ..., "XX.00123..FH1" up to all available streams.

To run the service, you should "cd" into the folder with the TDMS files and make sure that there is a file called "dasws.cfg" with its variables properly configured. Then, you can simply call the program, which will start and run as a daemon. The service will listen to all requests in port 8080.

The methods supported by the web service here provided are:

- query: The six required parameters "net", "sta", "loc", "cha", "start", and "end" are supported including their aliases. Errors are returned as specified in the standard.
- version: returns the version number in text/plain format.
- application.wadl: returns details about implemented and supported options and parameters.

All these methods are described in the global standard specification provided by the FDSN (see References).

2.7.2 Communities involvement

GEOFON (Germany), RESIF (France) and IRIS (USA), three of the most important seismological data centers at the global level, carried out this analysis of the new challenges imposed by this drastic change in data generation, and attempted to identify the needs of the community and to look for common solutions and best practices for managing very large data sets while maintaining their traditional data services.

We continue our international collaboration with data centers in order to find agreements, which could tentatively become standards. In the context of this task, we chaired a session in the European Seismological Conference on September 2021.

We expect to find broader agreements from the discussion in such international forums and groups. Ideally, in the long term, international standards and products should be developed within the framework of the FDSN. The next Plenary Meeting of the FDSN will be held on July 2023 in Berlin (GFZ being one of the organizers) and we expect to present and discuss some of these topics.

The package **dastools** will evolve with new functionality and our participation in the forums discussing how metadata should be defined for DAS experiments will be the input needed to enhance its functionality as soon as the discussions come to an agreement. Also, the definition by the community of the derived products from the DAS experiments will be included in all tools to support data center operators in producing standard products.

2.8 UC6.8: “Virtual definition of big datasets at seismological according to RDA recommendations”

2.8.1 The UC description

The management of digital objects remains an area of interest that crosses disciplines, institutions and infrastructures. In this context, the need for building aggregations or collections of such objects has become an essential element. Research data management practice requires not only to describe collections, but to make them actionable by automated processes to be able to cope with ever increasing amounts and volumes of data.

Collections are often described through metadata, and both within and across communities, suitable collection metadata schemas exist. It was however recognized that there is yet no single unified specification that enables the whole spectrum of create, read, update and delete (CRUD) actions that provide the necessary foundation for collection management tasks.

From the data centre perspective, it is sometimes difficult to offer many big pre-assembled datasets to be downloaded, when there is some overlap between them, increasing the storage space needed. Also, the support for versions in collections when only a small number of objects are changed in the whole dataset, because it could mean the duplication (or multiplication) of the storage space.

For instance, GEOFON (the seismological data centre of the GFZ) has archived seismic waveforms (continuous time series) since 1993 and currently archives around 10.000 streams daily from seismic stations sending data in real-time from all around the world (Quinteros et al, 2021).

We provide 100+ million user-defined datasets/year (not predefined datasets). It is impossible for us, mainly due to storage limitations, to replicate the requested datasets by keeping a copy of each of those. Therefore, there is no way for a user to reference the dataset for future use (publication, share with someone else). Today, the user can only share the request definition, but if there are new data in the requested time window or new streams in the set of stations defined the resulting dataset will be different from the original one.

In this context, the idea of using a Data Collections System is very appealing in order to define and save big pre-assembled datasets containing only “pointers” (e.g. PIDs, URLs) to the objects which are included. This would imply almost no extra storage, as only the pointers are stored. Therefore, big datasets could be offered through their definition with a marginal increase in the space needed.

Another benefit for this, is that a collection per-se does not need to exist or be stored in a central place but could actually be composed of resources from different data centres/sites. This is the case in seismology, in which users request data (define a dataset) and they transparently receive them from many data centres (Strollo et al, 2021).

This is a step beyond in the support for reproducibility, because once the definition of the dataset is specified, it can be later verified for any change, for instance via checksums.

In the case of the dynamic datasets the same approach could be followed. Namely, for each user requesting a dataset we could define a collection with the unique identifiers of the files that belong to the user definition/filter. If new data comes in the future, it will not appear in this original collection, because the content of the dataset will not be recreated based on the original query, but on the files which originally formed the collection.

In both cases, once a collection is created, it is possible for the user to reference it for later use (e.g., share it with others or use it as supplementary information for publications), which would imply a big step towards the reproducibility of results.

The final aim of this Task is to make the Data Collections System, originally developed by GEOFON for the seismological community, generic enough and ready to be adopted by others within the EOSC.

Activities carried out throughout the EOSC-Pillar project

The main outcome of this task was the release of the software package **datacoll**, based on the original development from GEOFON. This includes an implementation of the Data Collection web service, as well as a set of tools to work with it.

The **datacoll** package provides a library to access and manage collections in a Data Collection System. This consists of python classes which are the core of the tools provided. These classes can be imported by the users in their own code and include in it all the flexibility of **datacoll**.

The main functionality of the **datacoll** package is the implementation of its web service. By means of that, one can build collections within (or across) diverse domains and then sharing or expanding them across disciplines. This enables common tools for end-users and e-infrastructure providers. Individual disciplinary communities can directly benefit if such tools are made widely available, and cross-community data sharing can benefit from increased unification between collection models and implementations. A common API for data management of collections facilitates data interoperability and reuse by making solutions for managing collections more sustainable and widely available, encouraging better data management practices and allowing data objects in collections to be shared and re-used across domains. In the recommendation from the “Research Data Collection Systems WG”¹¹³ of the RDA the aim is not to propose an alternative to existing well established standards for describing and archiving collections, but rather to propose an API and implementation for creation, consumption, distribution and citation of collections and their items that could serve as a unifying layer on top of the existing models and which can enable producers and consumers of collections to operate on data items managed in diverse collection models and repositories (Weigel, et al, 2017).

From the general requirements on that recommendation, we think that is important to remark that:

- Objects in a collection must bear unique identifiers, which remain valid references throughout changes in object location within the system.
- Minimal state information on objects must remain retrievable using the identifier beyond the object’s lifetime.
- Objects may belong to more than one collection. This is a key factor for archives offering big datasets with considerable overlaps between them in order to save storage space.
- A single collection may contain objects stored at, and sourced from, different places.
- Collections must offer well-defined actions (such as create, read, update, delete) that can be executed by software agents with minimal additional context required.

Considering that this is a system considered lightweight we suggest that this could be easily deployed and run in a container. The system can be run from a docker container or from a normal server. If you would like to try the more classical installation, you can first clone the repository and then install it from the sources.

If you install it from the sources, you can then run the service with the command:

```
$ datacoll
```

In the next section you can see how an access token can be generated at the server.

To install the client utilities, you can skip the docker container and install it seamlessly by cloning and installing from the sources:

```
$ git clone https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/javier/datacoll.git  
$ cd datacoll  
$ sudo pip3 setup.py -e .
```

¹¹³ <http://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00022>

After this you should get in your path the following utilities specified in the next subsections. As with any service, not all operations are allowed to any user. Modifications to the data should be allowed only under the presentation of a JSON Web Token (JWT). This is one of the most-well know standards to be used in the authentication of agents in the realm of a service.

One of the tasks executed when the docker container is build is the creation of SSH keys (public and private) for the service. As usual, the private key will be used to generate and sign the tokens to be distributed to the users, while the public one will be used to validate its integrity at the moment of using the service. The gentoken utility supports the following usage.

```
usage: gentoken [-h] [-o OUTPUT] [-d DIR] [-m MAIL] [-n CN] [-e {1d,2d,1w,2w,1m}] [-V] [-v]
optional arguments:
  -h, --help            show this help message and exit
  -o OUTPUT, --output OUTPUT
                        Output file where to store the JWT token
  -d DIR, --dir DIR     Directory where the ".ssh" directory with keys can be found
  -m MAIL, --mail MAIL E-Mail address to encode in the token
  -n CN, --cn CN        Full name to encode in the token
  -e {1d,2d,1w,2w,1m}, --exp {1d,2d,1w,2w,1m}
                        Expiration time
  -V, --version          Show version information.
  -v, --verbose          Controls the verbosity of this script
```

The token can then be sent to the user and this can be used to operate with the Data Collections web service.

Examples

Generate a token for a researcher named “Javier Quinteros” with email address javier@gfz-potsdam.de and with an expiration of one month from now.

```
$ gentoken -m "javier@gfz-potsdam.de" -n "Javier Quinteros" -e "1m" -o ~/.eidajwt-jq -d "/opt/datacoll/datacoll"
```

The resulting token will look like the following.

```
$ cat ~/.eidajwt-jq
eyJ0eXAiOiJKV1QiLCJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiJ9.R2z9Fn3ESKfH85OIdGegR6MXwdqA-GW-k6-rQVY2QhnjGI7wSBv7KP-7DhWNkV4M8hnnFnZjopBz59rRGSCdArrPdNjZbVv4afGyj-l-g8hQd9Ylr2JOy75E03LrKFFZ8kRbx8NWVcJghHLPmHsh8MJyfaTIMEz89O6GLJod1XIF4hcMAJxWI
```

There are tools online to check what is the content of your token. For instance, if the token is pasted in the page at <https://jwt.io/> you can see the full content.

Figure 16: Example of a JWT Token for the system decoded at jwt.io.

To check that the web service deployed is working properly you can run the tests provided in the folder “tests”. The output, if everything is working as expected, should look like the following:

```
$ cd tests
$ python3 test01.py
Running test...
Checking Creation, query and deletion of a Collection.... [OK]
Checking Download of a whole Collection.... [OK]
Checking Filter collections by datatype of at least one of the members.... [OK]
Checking Try to retrieve a non-existing Collection.... [OK]
Checking Creation of a Collection by scanning a directory.... [OK]
Checking Creation of a Collection by scanning a directory without location for members.... [OK]
Checking List of Collections.... [OK]
Checking Format of cursors in list of collections.... [OK]
Checking Format of cursors in list of members.... [OK]
Checking 'features' method of the system.... [OK]
Checking Filter collections by owner.... [OK]
Checking Creation of a Collection in an invalid host.... [OK]
Checking Creation of a Collection with a valid licenseld.... [OK]
Checking Creation of a Collection with an invalid licenseld.... [OK]
Checking Creation of a Collection with a valid licenseld and reference.... [OK]
Checking Creation of a Collection with an invalid licenseld and reference.... [OK]
Checking Creation and deletion of a local Collection.... [OK]
Checking Creation and deletion of a local Member of a Collection.... [OK]
Checking Limit in the number of Members of a Collection.... [OK]
Checking Creation, query and deletion of a Member of a Collection.... [OK]
Checking Download of a Member.... [OK]
Checking Filter members by datatype... [OK]
Checking List of Members.... [OK]
Checking if the membershipIsMutable is properly implemented.... [OK]
```

Those tests cover the most important functionality from this system. CRUD operations with Collections and Members, as well as methods more related to the system itself.

The **dir2coll** utility allows you to create a collection from a set of files stored in a folder of your local storage.

The available parameters for this utility are:

```
% dir2coll -h
usage: dir2coll [-h] [-d DATA] [-n NAME] [-u URL] [-a AUTHENTICATION] [--dc DC] [-V] [-v VERBOSE]

optional arguments:
  -h, --help            show this help message and exit
  -d DATA, --data DATA  Root directory where the members of the collection are stored
  -n NAME, --name NAME   Name of the Collection. This attribute will be exported to other schemas (e.g. schema.org).
  -u URL, --url URL      Base of the URL (NOT including the filename) where the files will be publicly available
  -a AUTHENTICATION, --authentication AUTHENTICATION
                        Path or handle of the file containing the token to use during the authentication process
  --dc DC                URL of the Data Collection System. The default value is the one from the docker deployment
                        (http://localhost:8080/rda/datacoll)
  -V, --version          Show version information.
  -v VERBOSE, --verbose VERBOSE
                        Controls the verbosity of this script
```

An example to check this is the directory with example files which are included in the repository. Three files of different type are included: a spreadsheet, a Word document and a plain text file.

```
% ls -l testcoll
total 104
-rw-r--r-- 1 javier staff 21073 Dec 14 00:04 Excel.xlsx
-rw-r--r--@ 1 javier staff 21032 Dec 14 00:04 Word.docx
-rw-r--r-- 1 javier staff 5 Dec 14 00:04 text.txt
```

When this utility is run with the previous directory as source for the creation of the collection you should see the JSON summary in the output in parallel to the creation of the collection.

```
% dir2coll -d ./testcoll http://mydomain.ext/path/
{'capabilities': {'appendsToEnd': True,
  'isOrdered': True,
  'maxLength': -1,
  'membershipsMutable': True,
  'propertiesAreMutable': True,
  'restrictedToType': None,
  'ruleBasedGeneration': False,
  'supportsRoles': False},
'description': 'Created from the files in folder testcoll',
'id': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1ed9',
'properties': {'dateCreated': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.333000+00:00',
'descriptionOntology': '',
'hasAccessRestrictions': False,
'license': '',
'modelType': '',
'ownership': 'javier@gfz-potsdam.de'}}
{'checksum': '2205e48de5f93c784733ffcca841d2b5',
'collectionId': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1ed9',
'datatype': 'text/plain',
'description': '',
'id': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1eda',
'location': 'http://mydomain.ext/path/text.txt',
'mappings': {'dateAdded': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.348000+00:00',
'dateUpdated': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.348000+00:00',
'index': 0}}
{'checksum': '4d707d0edce75338514e4db65bbc1ba1',
'collectionId': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1ed9',
'datatype': 'application/vnd.openxmlformats-officedocument.wordprocessingml.document',
'description': '',
'id': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1edb',
'location': 'http://mydomain.ext/path/Word.docx',
'mappings': {'dateAdded': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.359000+00:00',
'dateUpdated': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.359000+00:00',
'index': 1}}
{'checksum': '18f25e2e6a69d5e44e67d8f487d6161c',
'collectionId': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1ed9',
'datatype': 'application/vnd.openxmlformats-officedocument.spreadsheetml.sheet',
'description': '',
'id': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1edc',
'location': 'http://mydomain.ext/path/Excel.xlsx',
'mappings': {'dateAdded': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.370000+00:00',
'dateUpdated': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.370000+00:00',
'index': 2}}
```

There, you can see the attributes of the collection and the members belonging to it. You can see that the datatype is guessed from a quick scan of the file, the checksum is calculated. Some of the functionality can be checked from a browser, as you can see in the next two figures. At least for methods that don't require any permission.

```

localhost:8080/rda/datacoll/collections/...
JSON
description : Created from the files in folder testcoll
properties
  dateCreated
    $date : 1666012243487
  ownership : javier@gfz-potsdam.de
  license :
  modelType :
  hasAccessRestrictions : false
  descriptionOntology :
capabilities
  isOrdered : true
  appendsToEnd : true
  supportsRoles : false
  membershipIsMutable : true
  propertiesAreMutable : true
  restrictedToType : null
  maxLength : -1
  ruleBasedGeneration : false
id : 634d54535df88d6c1a0f1ed5
    
```

Figure 17: JSON representation of a collection created from the “testcoll” directory from the repository.

```

localhost:8080/rda/datacoll/collections/61b7dfd5f74dc2ea7df23482...
JSON :
0
  _id
  $oid : 61b7dfd5f74dc2ea7df23482
  _collectionId
  $oid : 61b7dfd5f74dc2ea7df23481
  location : http://localhost:8080/rda/datacoll/testcoll/text.txt
  checksum :
  datatype : text/plain
  mappings
    index : 0
    dateAdded
      $date : 1639440341095
    dateUpdated
      $date : 1639440341095
1
  _id
  $oid : 61b7dfd5f74dc2ea7df23483
  _collectionId
  $oid : 61b7dfd5f74dc2ea7df23481
  location : http://localhost:8080/rda/datacoll/testcoll/Word.docx
  checksum :
  datatype : application/vnd.openxmlformats-officedocument.wordprocessingml.document
  mappings
    index : 1
    dateAdded
      $date : 1639440341121
    dateUpdated
      $date : 1639440341121
2
  _id
  $oid : 61b7dfd5f74dc2ea7df23484
  _collectionId
  $oid : 61b7dfd5f74dc2ea7df23481
  location : http://localhost:8080/rda/datacoll/testcoll/Excel.xlsx
  checksum :
    
```

Figure 18: Some of the members in the collection from the same example above.

dcclient is a client provided in the repository to manage and use the Data Collection System. The available parameters and commands are:

```
% dcclient -h
usage: dcclient [-h] [-a AUTHENTICATION] [--dc DC] [-V] [-v VERBOSE] {create,add,delete,list,shortlist,show,download} ...
```

```
positional arguments:
  {create,add,delete,list,shortlist,show,download}
  sub-command help
```

```
create      Command to create a collection
add        Command to add a member to a collection
delete     Command to delete a collection or member
list       Command to list collections or members
shortlist  Command to list collections or members in one line
show      Command to show details of one collection or member
download   Command to download a collection or a member
```

optional arguments:

```
-h, --help      show this help message and exit
-a AUTHENTICATION, --authentication AUTHENTICATION
                File containing the token to use during the authentication process
--dc DC         URL of the Data Collection System. The default value is the one from the docker deployment
                (http://localhost:8080/rda/datacoll)
-V, --version   Show version information.
-v VERBOSE, --verbose VERBOSE
                Controls the verbosity of this script
```

These are some of the examples that could be executed with this client.

Get a list of the collections defined:

```
0:
{'capabilities': {'appendsToEnd': True,
                 'isOrdered': True,
                 'maxLength': -1,
                 'membershipsMutable': True,
                 'propertiesAreMutable': True,
                 'restrictedToType': None,
                 'ruleBasedGeneration': False,
                 'supportsRoles': False},
 'description': 'Created from the files in folder testcoll',
 'id': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1ed9',
 'properties': {'dateCreated': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.333000+00:00',
               'descriptionOntology': '',
               'hasAccessRestrictions': False,
               'license': '',
               'modelType': '',
               'ownership': 'javier@gfz-potsdam.de'}}
```

Get members from one collection in particular:

```
$ dcclient list 634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1ed9
0:
{'checksum': '2205e48de5f93c784733ffcca841d2b5',
 'collectionId': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1ed9',
 'datatype': 'text/plain',
 'description': '',
 'id': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1eda',
 'location': 'http://mydomain.ext/path/text.txt',
 'mappings': {'dateAdded': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.348000+00:00',
              'dateUpdated': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.398000+00:00',
              'index': 0}}
1:
{'checksum': '4d707d0edce75338514e4db65bbc1ba1',
 'collectionId': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1ed9',
 'datatype': 'application/vnd.openxmlformats-officedocument.wordprocessingml.document',
 'description': '',
 'id': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1edb',
 'location': 'http://mydomain.ext/path/Word.docx',
 'mappings': {'dateAdded': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.359000+00:00',
              'dateUpdated': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.413000+00:00',
              'index': 1}}
2:
{'checksum': '18f25e2e6a69d5e44e67d8f487d6161c',
 'collectionId': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1ed9',
 'datatype': 'application/vnd.openxmlformats-officedocument.spreadsheetml.sheet',
```

```
'description': '',  
'id': '634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1edc',  
'location': 'http://mydomain.ext/path/Excel.xlsx',  
'mappings': {'dateAdded': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.370000+00:00',  
             'dateUpdated': '2022-10-17T16:46:55.428000+00:00',  
             'index': 2}}
```

Remove a member from a collection

```
$ dcclient delete 634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1ed9 634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1eda  
Member removed: 634d86ff5df88d6c1a0f1eda
```

Docker container

In order to allow different service providers to adopt this implementation, a docker container is provided with the server and client software, as well as the background mongoDB storage. To deploy and run the service from a container you should follow the next steps. Clone the repository, build the container and run it in detached mode.

```
$ git clone https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/javier/datacoll.git  
$ cd datacoll  
$ docker build -t datacoll .  
$ docker run -d --publish 8080:8080 --name datacoll datacoll
```

Please, remember to generate a token as specified in section 2.3 and to save it in the home folder of the user accessing the system (~/.eidajwt). If you have followed carefully these instructions, you should be able to start using the system.

2.8.2 2.8.2 Communities involvement

The main input used within this task was, first, the one collected through the life of the RDA WG. During the initial stages of this project we expand this to other seismological data centres (originally only GEOFON-GFZ) and the seismological community in general, as well as the climatological community (DKRZ).

After the implementation and putting the system in production, we are working on the inclusion of this system as an important link between the already standard data provisioning systems and a system that could provide long-term archival of user defined datasets. We are advertising it and doing first tests for the adoption on communities like EIDA (currently 12 data centers).

2.9 UC6.9: “Integrating heterogeneous data on cultural heritage”

2.9.1 The UC description

Heritage Sciences, i.e., the application of scientific experimental methods to the analysis of cultural heritage artifacts, produces a large quantity of numeric data that are only loosely related to the cultural object to which the analyses were applied. The lack of standard data models for the different technologies employed makes interoperability between datasets almost impossible. On the other hand, the same cultural objects and activities on them (studies, interventions, etc.) are documented in textual documents usually with very basic metadata. This situation requires the intervention of a human to link the documentation of scientific analyses to the documentation of the cultural object, e.g., chemical analyses and physical to a study by an art historian; this in the end prevents data re-use and data-driven research. The creation of a Linked Data system requires the creation of a common semantic model covering both the scientific data and the content of text reports.

This requires an application profile of CIDOC CRM, the standard ontology used for cultural heritage documentation, based on previous extensions such as CRM-PE, developed within the PARTHENOS project, and CRM-SCI. Based on this newly created schema, the data encoding may be obtained by uploading the numeric results of the scientific experiments together with their metadata to create the scientific side; and then uploading the text data annotated with the same ontology. The system will then create the links between the two components of the documentation system. However, the manual annotation of texts is cumbersome and time consuming. The use case proposes a text mining tool based on machine learning to automatically enrich the metadata of the texts by NER (Named Entity Recognition), which may then be linked to the metadata accompanying the digital outcomes of the scientific analyses, both being organized with the same ontology.

In this perspective, in the framework of the EOSC-Pillar, Tools for HERitage Science Processing, Integration, and ANalysis (THESPIAN) was developed (figure 19). THESPIAN is a cloud system offering multiple web services to the researchers of the Cultural Heritage Network (CHNet) of INFN (Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare). The mission of CHNet is to harmonise and enhance the expertise of the Institute in the field of Cultural Heritage, expertise distributed among many structures spread over the whole Italian territory. CHNet includes the INFN research groups whose activity is devoted to the development and application of technologies for the study and conservation of Cultural Heritage, but it is open also to other national partners with expertise complementary to that of the Institute and to international partners engaged in diagnostics in cultural heritage.

The purpose of the THESPIAN platform is to create a web ecosystem for storage, retrieval and analysis of scientific data coming from physical analysis on cultural heritage, and their metadata, modelled according to the state-of-the-art ontologies and standards, and to make them interoperable with data accessible on other platforms, according to the FAIR principles for data: findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

Figure 19: Visual schema on how the THESPIAN-NER service operates.

THESPIAN Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) part of the platform has been integrated into the INFN Cloud Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS), so that INFN-CHNet users can still access the web resources, now relying on the infrastructure and platform services designed, developed, and offered by the INFN Center for Research and Development on Information and Communication Technologies (CNAF).

The main goal of such cloud service is to offer various software services, as THESPIAN-Mask, a service to store raw data and their metadata regarding scientific analysis on Cultural Heritage through a shared ontology implemented via a web service. After that, each researcher of the network may use and re-use their data, as well as the available data of all the other researchers of the network and analyse such data using a set of web services hosted in the cloud.

Metadata Form for Cultural Heritage Network

[Go to Metadatamask Homepage](#)

1 Study Object	Name*: <input type="text" value="Mona Lisa"/>	?	Search WikiData <input type="text" value="Q"/>
	Study object name		
	Type*: <input type="text"/>	?	Search AAT <input type="text" value="Q"/>
	Study object type		
	Author: <input type="text" value="Leonardo da Vinci"/>	?	Search ULAN <input type="text" value="Q"/>
	Study object author		
	Period: <input type="text" value="Rinascimento (Italy)"/>	?	Search PeriodO <input type="text" value="Q"/>
	Study object period		
Period Span:	<input type="text" value="Start date (e.g. 1300)"/>		<input type="text" value="End date (e.g. 1360)"/>
	Study object period Span: Start date		Study object period Span: End date
Location Label:	<input type="text" value="Salle des Etats"/>		
	Study object Location label		
Location:	<input type="button" value="pick place"/>	<input type="button" value="reset coordinates"/>	<input type="text" value="geo:48.861020,2.3358700"/>
			Study Object location (as geo URI standard schema)

Figure 20: View of the THESPIAN-Mask page devoted to the insertion of a new metadata record. The buttons for accessing third party's APIs are shown.

The goal is thus to have data which are *findable, accessible, interoperable* and *reusable* (FAIR).

The tool is tailored on a metadata model based on CRMhs, an extension of the CIDOC CRM ontology CIDOC_CRM, designed for modeling the complex entities typical of heritage science, developed by INFN and VAST-LAB PIN (Figure 20).

To help the user navigate the scientific database created by THESPIAN-Mask, and to ease the burden of metadata generation, an additional web service was developed: THESPIAN-NER, a Natural Language Processing (NLP) tool for automatic Named Entity Recognition (NER). THESPIAN-NER allows users to

1. (semi)automatically generate custom THESPIAN-Mask queries, by similarity with a certain Italian written documents or reports;
2. (semi)automatically fill-in a certain number of THESPIAN-Mask metadata fields, again by similarity with a certain Italian written documents or reports;

This is because the NLP NER models, hosted in the Cloud, are capable of automatically annotating either archaeological documents or scientific reports written in Italian (either from .txt or .pdf files), by identifying and labelling relevant semantic entities. Those labels are in correspondence with CRMhs ontology (Classes, Properties), as well as metadata fields.

THESPIAN-NER - Named Entity Recognition tool for Archeology

Collaborative semantic enrichment of text-based datasets - Italian language version

primi scavi ACT nell'area pompeiana si ebbero a partire dal 1748 TSP , per volere di Carlo III di Borbone a seguito del successo dei ritrovamenti di Ercolano SIT : i sondaggi ACT furono svolti da Roque Joaquín de Alcubierre, che, credendo di essere sulle tracce dell'antica Stabiae, riportò alla luce nei pressi della collina di Civita SIT diverse monete ART e oggetti d'epoca romana PRD , oltre a porzioni di costruzioni, prontamente ricoperte dopo l'esplorazione. Le esplorazioni furono ben presto abbandonate a causa degli scarsi ritrovamenti e ripresero soltanto nel 1754 TSP : nel 1763 TSP , grazie al rinvenimento di un'epigrafe ART , che parlava chiaramente della Res Publica Pompeianorum, si intuì che si trattava dell'antica città di Pompei[11]. Con Maria Carolina, moglie di Ferdinando IV PER , e l'ingegnere Francesco La Vega, parte della città, come la zona dei teatri, il tempio di Iside ART , il Foro Triangolare, diverse case e necropoli vennero SIT riportate completamente alla luce e non più seppellite, ma rimaste a vista; fu durante il dominio francese, con a capo Giocchino Murat e la moglie Carolina, che gli scavi godettero di un momento di

Use extractive text summarisation Download as html Download as .txt

Timespan	Number of Timespan found in the text: 11
Artefacts	Number of Artefacts found in the text: 7
Site	Number of Site found in the text: 4
Location	Number of Location found in the text: 4
Person	Number of Person found in the text: 2
Activity	Number of Activity found in the text: 2
Period	Number of Period found in the text: 1
Organisation	Number of Organisation found in the text: 0
Biological Remains	Number of Biological Remains found in the text: 0

Number of selected entities: 0

Figure 21: The NER web-page after the ArcheoNER analysis. It is easy to see the labels ordered by the number of entities found. On the left, under the annotated text, it is possible to see the button to be clicked for showing the summarised text.

The entities can thus be extracted and used for building custom queries to fetch related records available on the CHNet database, or to fill some metadata fields, exploiting the labels relation with the NoSQL, JSON-based realization of the database structure.

THESPIAN-NER models are two ad-hoc trained neural networks: ArcheoNER, for processing archaeological texts, and \textit{hsNER}, for Scientific Reports of Analysis on Cultural Heritage. These models were built using the open-source python package spaCy and fine-tuned using transfer learning to classify named entities with the aforementioned custom labels.

The screenshot shows the THESPIAN-NER web interface. At the top, it says "THESPIAN-NER - Named Entity Recognition tool for Archeology". Below that, it says "Collaborative semantic enrichment of text-based datasets - Italian language version". The main part of the interface shows a text snippet with several entities highlighted in colored boxes: "primi scavi" (ACT), "dal 1748" (TSP), "Ercolano" (SIT), "sondaggi" (ACT), "Civita" (SIT), "monete" (ART), "d'epoca romana" (PRD), "nel 1754" (TSP), "nel 1763" (TSP), "un'epigrafe" (ART), "Ferdinando IV" (PER), "tempio di Iside" (ART), "necropoli vennero" (SIT), and "Nel 1980" (TSP). Below the text, there are buttons for "Use extractive text summarisation", "Download as html", and "Download as .txt".

The "Timespan" section is expanded, showing a list of time periods with their respective number of appearances in the text and a checkbox for selection:

Timespan	Number of Timespan found in the text: 11	Selection
dal 1748	(number of appearances in the text: 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
nel 1754	(number of appearances in the text: 1)	<input type="checkbox"/>
nel 1763	(number of appearances in the text: 1)	<input type="checkbox"/>
nel 1863	(number of appearances in the text: 1)	<input type="checkbox"/>
tra il 1870 e il 1885	(number of appearances in the text: 1)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Durante il XX secolo	(number of appearances in the text: 1)	<input type="checkbox"/>
A partire dagli anni	(number of appearances in the text: 1)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nel 1980	(number of appearances in the text: 1)	<input type="checkbox"/>

At the bottom, there are buttons for "Generate metadata", "Search database with selected entities - OR", and "Search database with selected entities - AND".

Figure 22: The NER web-page after the ArcheoNER analysis. In the opened Time span section, the list of entities are shown; The button for the entity selection can be seen on the right of the entity's name. In the bottom right is possible to see the two buttons for querying the database, while in the bottom left is possible to see the number of the chosen entities and the button to generate the pre-filled metadata mask and open it in the THESPIAN-Mask page.

To recap, THESPIAN-NER offers authorized users the possibility of either generating queries on the CHNet database (semi)automatically, or fill in some metadata fields, starting from Italian written documents and reports of either archaeological or heritage scientific topics; it is performed entirely via a user-friendly web graphical interface. The app is deployed as a service in the CHNet integrated Cloud environment, compliant with FAIR rules.

2.9.2 Communities involvement

The main community involved so far is the archaeological community, which showed interest in developing applications to archaeometry documentation. In general, the main issue is the scarce availability of digital documentation in the cultural heritage domain.

2.10 T6.10: “New thematic services from EOSC-Pillar open call”

in the frame of the WP6, an open call for thematic services has been launched end of 2020 with the aim of broadening the thematic scope of the nine already defined WP6 Use cases and of giving additional non-conventional services the possibility to be supported by the experts associated in EOSC-Pillar. In total eight applications have been received, six of them have been selected as potential new Use cases to be mentored within the project. The six selected applicants were invited to present their services in detail during a dedicated virtual hackathon organized in June 2021. It was the occasion for the service providers to specify exactly their needs and define joint support activities with the experts of the project. Finally, five service providers accepted to be part of the project as “new Use cases”. They are listed here below.

2.10.1 Ethnic and Migrant Minorities’(EMM)Survey Registry *proposed by SciencesPo (France)*

The EMM Survey Registry, jointly developed by the COST Action ETHMIG SURVEY DATA, the H2020 project SSHOC (Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud) and the French ANR project FAIRETHMIGQUANT, is a free online service for discovering and learning about existing quantitative surveys undertaken with EMM (sub)populations in Europe and beyond. It offers detailed and structured metadata for each of the surveys it documents. The EMM Survey Registry has two interfaces: the front-end and back-end. The front-end is where all the metadata is made available for discovery, access, and re-use. The back-end is where the metadata itself is managed and is where new metadata can be directly contributed to the EMM Survey Registry. The registry is intended for anyone interested in learning about and/or using quantitative survey data on EMMs’ integration and/or inclusion, such as (non)academic researchers and policymakers. It’s also of interest for data producers of quantitative surveys with EMM respondents.

Contact: sshoc.project@sciencespo.fr

Access the resource

<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/ethnic-and-migrant-minority-survey-registry/offers>

2.10.2 MMODA (Multi-Messenger Online Data Analysis) *proposed by ISDC Data Centre for Astrophysics (University of Geneva, Switzerland) and “Laboratoire AstroParticule et Cosmologie (APC)” (Paris, France)*

The MMODA service (formerly known as AstroODA - Astrophysical Online Data Analysis) allows users to leverage cloud-based scientific data analysis workflows of astrophysical observatories/experiments: INTEGRAL, POLAR, ANTARES, LIGO/Virgo, and SDSS (LegacySurvey) observatories (with further resources under development), providing verified publication ready results.

This service primarily targets researchers and research groups in the astrophysical field.

Contact: contact@odahub.io

Access the resource

<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/astronomical-online-data-analysis-astrooda>

2.10.3 ReadMETRICS

proposed by Inist-CNRS and Couperin.org (France)

ReadMETRICS is a new turnkey solution for

- monitoring transformative agreements, including before and beyond;
- analyzing usage across disciplines and consortia;
- assessing value of publishing spend;
- enabling comparative citation analysis.

It is based on the already existing and field-tested ezPAARSE and ezMESURE free and open-source tools, extending and including features inspired by the National Library of Luxembourg's transition to Open Access. Users of the service can for example be universities, hospitals, research libraries, or even institutions consortia, subscribing to various electronic resources packages that need to collect and aggregate usage data to that content.

Contact: readmetrics@couperin.org

2.10.4 SIMBAD

proposed by CDS (Strasbourg astronomical Data Center, Strasbourg, France)

SIMBAD is the reference database for the nomenclature and bibliography of astronomical objects (outside the solar system), provided by CDS as one of its services for the astronomy research community.

Typical users of the service are astrophysics researchers around the world, but also amateur astronomers, educators, planetaria and the general public. The service may also be of interest for users from other disciplines like citizen science.

Astronomical observatories, space agencies (e.g. NASA, ESA, JAXA), astronomy data centres, and data archives integrate calls to SIMBAD into their own systems, i.e. for 'name resolving' of astronomical object names and coordinates. Many astronomy software tools and services integrate calls to SIMBAD.

Contact: cds-question@unistra.fr

Access the resource

<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/simbad-provides-basic-data-cross-ids-bibliography-and-measurements-for-astronomical-objects-outside-the-solar-system/offers>

2.10.5 Thoth

proposed by University Lancaster (UK)

Thoth is an Open Metadata Service for Open Access Books that assists publishers in managing openly licensed, standardscompliant bibliographic metadata for open access books, and opens gateways for metadata records to flow into dissemination, discovery, and preservation infrastructures.

The primary users of Thoth are open access book publishers who will use the services to manage and disseminate bibliographic metadata for the titles they publish. Beyond that, Thoth can also be interesting for library publishing programs, university presses, or even commercial open access publishers, who are struggling with the incoherence of the open access book supply chain too.

Contact: thoth@copim.ac.uk

Since July 2021, these service providers received different kind of support from the EOSC-Pillar experts, starting with connecting them with appropriate initiatives and projects, but also Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) integration support, support regarding hosting issues, provision of computational resources, provision of a testing framework for Jupyter Notebook, and finally support for the onboarding process for registration in the EOSC Marketplace. To date **EMM Survey Registry**, **MMODA**, and **SIMBAD** have been successfully onboarded to EOSC Marketplace.

3 Cross-cutting analysis

Considering the specific objectives of WP6 oriented to analyse the genericity of tools and services from the Use Cases as well as to develop cross-cutting approaches, platforms and demonstrators, since the beginning of the activities a particular attention has been paid to both the identification and the implementation of possible linkages among “disciplinary” Use cases on one hand, and between Use cases and other technical parts of the project, namely WP5 and WP7 on the other hand. Indeed, the methodology adopted since the state of the art (D6.1) has been structured around these two main analysis criteria. Several specific meetings have been held at the WP level in coordination with the other WPs, as well as one-to-one meetings have been organized by the most of the Use cases. In some cases, transversal collaboration was particularly efficient due to the similarity of technical aspects addressed and to the participation of some consortium members to several Use cases, as, for instance, in the case of UC1 and UC2, or UC3 and UC6. Here below, the matrix synthetising the most relevant collaborations developed and implemented by the Use cases.

UC	6.1	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.5	6.6	6.7	6.8	6.9	WP5	WP7
6.1		<p>The climate demonstrators have been brought into the EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE developed in the context of UC6.2, thus providing not only data analytics capabilities, but also guidance and kick-start tools for the generation of PROV documents compliant with the W3C PROV standard, thus addressing the FAIR principles at a finer granularity. In this regard, it is worth mentioning two main activities:</p> <p>1. Provenance procedures added to data analysis Jupyter notebooks: The <i>EOSCPillar4EarthScience</i> JupyterLab Notebook for creating an interactive plot of the Global Yearly Mean Anomaly of a CMIP6 variable has been extended</p>						<p>Generation and integration of PIDs in provenance records. The added provenance information in the data analysis notebook includes the PIDs of all data, which go into the analysis and hence provides a link to UC6.8, which uses PIDs for the definition of large data collections.</p>		<p>T5.1 & 5.2: as described in the previous section, some of the datasets used to set up the proof-of-concept climate use cases were described through the EOSC-Pillar Federated FAIR Data Space (F2DS) and published into the D4Science EOSC-Pillar Data Catalog.</p> <p>T5.3: a guidelines document about the implemented demonstrator has been published into the EOSC-Pillar Training and Support Catalogue, thus</p>	<p>EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE</p>

		<p>with first-level provenance information.</p> <p>2. Containerization of the Ophidia HPDA framework including provenance support. The <i>EOSCPillar4EarthScience</i> JupyterLab environment has been extended to include an instance of the Ophidia HPDA framework for running parallel, in-memory, server-side data analysis. In this way, users can easily integrate an Ophidia-based analysis (through the PyOphidia programmatic interface included in the Python-based software stack) into a more articulated data analytics workflow; then, based on the information about the executed analytics operators that are tracked by the Ophidia analytics engine, they can get fine-grained (second-level) provenance information represented according to the W3C PROV specifications.</p>							<p>contributing to the UC5.3 activities in terms of documentation and online help for promoting FAIR practices and support to FAIR-oriented data stewardship. The document is also available on the Zenodo open data repository.</p>	
6.2	Cf.6.1			Cf.6.4				<p>UC6.2 has provided community feedback about a specification on Data Collection System proposed by</p>	<p>T5.1 & 5.2: the most relevant climate and ocean datasets were described through the EOSC-Pillar Federated FAIR Data Space (F2DS) and published into the D4Science</p>	<p>EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE</p>

										how the demonstrator try to address FAIR-compliance.	
6.3						Cf.6.6					
6.4		Interest in integrating Software Heritage into the Pangeo community platform.	Interest into integrating the Dataverse platform into the Software Heritage archive, similarly to what has been already done for the Zenodo/Invenio RDM platform.								The authentication service of the Software Heritage Archive has been linked with KIT Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) as part of the WP7 effort to help EOSC partners interested in integrating Software Heritage services in their platform.
6.5											Cf. Additional UC (pag.30)
6.6			The provision of a prototype for Insem Repository, used as data source for testing UC6.6 workflows, has been established in collaboration with UC6.3 led by INRAE.								
6.7											Capability to stage the data requested in different cloud services provided by WP7 (e.g. Nextcloud), or HPC facilities by means of services like Globus.
6.8							Internal link is with UC6.7, by means of the creation of a collection for each user-defined requests in the data provisioning system of the seismological community. This will				

							improve the reproducibility of the results in published papers, as the initial dataset (always unique and user-defined) could be registered and identified.					
6.9												

4 Conclusions

This deliverable documents the technical developments and other activities implementation such as those related to the communities involvement, the development of training materials and outreach actions promoted by WP6 Use cases. According to the WP6 general objective to prepare scientific communities to be involved in EOSC, the Use cases have mainly achieved specific community-tailored results through the development of specific services and demonstrators. Moreover, throughout the entire cycle of the project each Use case, starting from the analysis of the specificities of scientific communities, tried to break down disciplinary silos and to consequently develop cross-cutting approaches. In this case, the results achieved are quite different in reason of the maturity level of the technical developments on one hand, and of the similarity in terms of technical requirements and scientific needs from communities involved on the other. Finally, all the Use cases partners and participants have been involved in different activities in terms of scientific vulgarisation and outreach often in coordination with WP2 in charge of communication and with WP5 as well for any activities in relation with training and education.

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